

WaysTUP!

VALUE CHAINS FOR DISRUPTIVE TRANSFORMATION OF URBAN
BIOWASTE INTO BIOBASED PRODUCTS IN THE CITY CONTEXT

D3.10: Report on demonstration of PILOT 1 (Final)

WP3 – Demonstration of urban biowaste utilization through PILOTs operation

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Table of contents

1. Introduction	13
1.1. Pilot overview and objectives	13
1.2. Bioprocess' description	14
1.1.1. Production of carotenoids from spent coffee ground (SCG).....	14
1.1.2. Extraction of oils and polyphenols from SCGs.....	15
1.1.3. Production of gelatin and active peptides from meat and fish by-products.....	15
1.3. Bioproducts and potential applications.....	16
1.3.1. Carotenoids.....	16
1.3.2. Oils and polyphenols.....	17
1.3.3. Gelatin and active peptides.....	17
1.3.4. Organic fertilizers.....	18
1.4. State of the art of the biowaste valorization	18
1.4.1. Spent Coffee Grounds valorization.....	19
1.4.2. Meat and fish by-products valorization.....	19
2. Methodology	21
2.1. Logistics for biowaste collection	21
2.1.1. Spent Coffee Grounds.....	21
2.1.2. Fish by-products.....	22
2.1.3. Meat by-products.....	24
2.2. Feedstock characterization	25
2.2.1. Determination of Total Solids	25
2.2.2. Extraction of fats.....	26
2.2.3. Monounsaturated and polyunsaturated fat content	26
2.2.4. Protein analysis	26
2.2.5. Carbohydrates content analysis	26
2.3. Bioprocess steps and equipment	26
2.3.1. Carotenoids production from Spent Coffee Grounds through fermentation.....	26
2.3.2. Extraction of oils and polyphenols from Spent Coffee Grounds.....	28
2.3.3. Production of gelatine and active peptides from fish and meat by-products.....	30
2.4. Pilot scale trials	35
2.4.1. Production of carotenoids from SCGs.....	35
2.4.2. Extraction of oils and polyphenols from SCG.....	38
2.4.3. Production of gelatin from fish by-products	39
2.4.4. Production of enzymes and active peptides from meat by-products	42
2.5. Valorisation of the exhausted solids	43
2.6. Analytical methods.....	43
2.6.1. Biomass production	43
2.6.2. Glucose quantification	43

2.6.3. Oils and polyphenols quantification.....	44
3. Results of demonstration phase.....	45
3.1 Structural composition of the feedstocks.....	45
3.2 Production of carotenoids from spent coffee grounds.....	46
3.2.1 Sugar release from SCG's enzymatic hydrolysis.....	46
3.2.2 Carotenoids production from SCG.....	50
3.2.3 Production of gelatin from meat by-products.....	58
3.2.4 Production of gelatin from fish by-products.....	64
3.2.5 Production of organic fertilizer from meat by-products.....	68
3.2.6 Extraction of oil and polyphenols.....	69
4. Economic Analysis.....	77
5. Conclusions.....	86
6. References.....	89

List of Tables

Table 1. Pilot 1 Overview	14
Table 2. Chemical composition of spent coffee ground (Ballesteros et al., 2014; Obruca et al., 2015; Perta-Crisan et al., 2019).	15
Table 3. Initial enzymatic hydrolysis trials through enzymatic screening	36
Table 4. Enzymatic hydrolysis tests using Celluclast 1.5 L (E1) and Vinotaste Pro (E2) at different concentrations	37
Table 5. Parameters conditions for the production of carotenoids. Bioprocess's steps and different tests.	38
Table 6. Trials and steps for the production of gelatin from fish by-products. Muscle meat and viscera of multiple big fishes (MMV); small fishes (SM); salmon heads, bones and skins (SHBS).	39
Table 7. Pre-layer formation tests using different dosages of Celite 545®	40
Table 8. Layer formation tests using different dosages of Celite Hyflo Super-Cel	41
Table 9. Trials and steps for the production of gelatin from fish by-products (salmon heads, bones and skins (SHBS)).	41
Table 10. Chemical blood hydrolysis steps and parameters.	43
Table 11. Structural composition of dried meat by-products	45
Table 12. Structural composition of dried fish by-products	45
Table 13. Structural composition of dried spent coffee grounds	46
Table 14. Enzymatic SCGs hydrolysis trial for the obtention of glucose.	47
Table 15. Coffee hydrolysis with 2 enzymes (consecutive addition). Hydrolyzed with an enzyme during 12 hours and 12 hours later with another enzyme at 50°C and pH 4.5	47
Table 16. Trial based on pH optimization in enzymatic hydrolysis of SCGs using Celluclast enzyme.	48
Table 17. Enzymatic hydrolysis trial with two enzymes added at the beginning of the trial.	48
Table 18. Hydrolysis SCG trial with the addition of two enzymes sequentially.	48
Table 19. Glucose release from SCG's enzymatic hydrolysis.	49
Table 20. Monitoring results of laboratory fermentation for carotenoid production	51
Table 21. SAV pilot plant fermentation tests for carotenoid production.	52
Table 22. Cell wet weight (g/L) results for CAR-1 and CAR-2 fermentation tests.	52
Table 23. Cell dry weight (g/L) results for CAR-1 and CAR-2 fermentation tests	53
Table 24. Cell dry weight (g/L) results from CAR-5 to CAR-13 fermentation tests	54

Table 25. Trials with different NaPOH concentrations (Sample 1: 1,25%, Sample 2: 2.5%; Sample 3: 5%)	59
Table 26. Neutral and alkaline maceration results.	59
Table 27. Enzymatic hydrolysis results.	60
Table 28. Alkaline and Neutral maceration results in C and D samples.	61
Table 29. Thermal extraction results.	62
Table 30. Enzymatic hydrolysis results	64
Table 31. Gelatin production from fish by-products	64
Table 32. Dosage and conditions of the FRAP essays	65
Table 33. Fe ²⁺ concentration (μM) of the FRAP essays for different proteases	65
Table 34. Trials and steps for the production of hydrolyzed collagen from fish by-products (salmon skins).	66
Table 35. Hydrolysate blood parameters.	69
Table 36. Fatty acid distribution for SCG	70
Table 37. Actual extract volume concentration	75
Table 38. Average price for products tested in Pilot 1	77
Table 39. Gain percentage from MBV in biofertilizer production.	78
Table 40. Gain percentage from MBV in oil extraction.	79
Table 41. Gain percentage from MBV in carotenoid extraction	80
Table 42. Gain percentage from MBV in gelatin production	82
Table 43. Gain percentage from MBV in hydrolyzed collagen production	83
Table 44. Gain percentage from MBV in polyphenols extraction	85

List of Figures

Figure 1. Container designed for the collection of SCG.	21
Figure 2. Spent coffee ground collection system developed in the city of Valencia. From restaurants to the Bioprocess Demonstrative Facility of SAV.	21
Figure 3. Logistics for fish by-products collection	22
Figure 4. 1 tn of salmon by-products received for gelatine and hydrolyzed collagen production.	23
Figure 5. Pictures of large fish by-products received.	24
Figure 6. Rabbit dried skin as feedstock for the production of enzymes and active peptides.	25
Figure 7. Bioprocess diagram for the carotenoids production.	27
Figure 8. Equipment used for the carotenoid production. From left to right: hydrolysis reactor, fermenter, tangential flow filtration (TFF) and homogenizer.	28
Figure 9. Carotenoids product after PONY homogenization	28
Figure 10. Bioprocess diagram for the oils and polyphenols extraction.	29
Figure 11. Solid-liquid extraction of oils and polyphenols from SCG in pilot Soxhlet equipment.	29
Figure 12. Salmon by-products (left) and product after crushed (right).	30
Figure 13. Solid remains after the maceration and rotary sieve that will enter in the extraction tank.	31
Figure 14. Maceration process in 1,5 m3 tank.	31
Figure 15. Filter press cloth after the separation of remaining solids.	32
Figure 16. Bioprocess diagram for the gelatin and hydrolyzed collagen production from fish and meat by-products.	33
Figure 17. Gelatine drying at the SAV's drum dryer.	34
Figure 18. Bioprocess diagram for the production of enzymes and active peptides from blood	35
Figure 19. Cell Dry biomass variation along the fermentation for CAR-5 to CAR-13	55
Figure 20. Y-Astaxanthin concentration in tests CAR-5 to CAR-13	56
Figure 21. Cell Dry biomass variation along the fermentation. for CAR-S1	57
Figure 22. Cell Dry biomass variation along the fermentation for CAR-5 to CAR-13 and CAR-S1	57
Figure 23. Y-Astaxanthin concentration in tests CAR-5 to CAR-13 and CAR-S1	58
Figure 24. Chemical treatment determination. Neutral, Acid and Basic.	58
Figure 25. A and B samples after maceration and Enzymatic hydrolysis.	60

Figure 26. Exhausted solids A and B.	61
Figure 27. Solids C and D after alkaline and neutral maceration process, respectively.	61
Figure 28. Result of thermal extraction.	62
Figure 29. Exhausted solid from tests C and D after maceration and thermal extraction.	63
Figure 30. Liquid resulting from the gelatin extraction process.	63
Figure 31. Gelatine (left) and hydrolyzed collagen (right) produced from fish by-products.	68
Figure 32. Soxhlet during the SCG oil extraction with hexane.	71
Figure 33. Rotavapor of 20 liters capacity during the coffee oil/hexane separation.	71
Figure 34. Sample of coffee oil extracted from the SCGs.	72
Figure 35. Soxhlet during polyphenol extraction from SCG.	72
Figure 36. GAE concentration (mg/L) obtained after solid-liquid extraction.	73
Figure 37. mg of Gallic Acid per g of SCG obtained after solid-liquid extraction.	73
Figure 38. GAE concentration (mg/L) obtained after liquid-liquid extraction.	74
Figure 39. mg of Gallic Acid per g of SCG obtained after liquid-liquid extraction.	74
Figure 40. MVB growth from year 1 to year 10 of bio-fertilizer from blood.	78
Figure 41. MVB growth from year 1 to year 10 of oils extraction.	80
Figure 42. MVB growth from year 1 to year 10 of carotenoid production.	81
Figure 43. MVB growth from year 1 to year 10 of gelatin production.	82
Figure 44. MVB growth from year 1 to year 10 of hydrolyzed collagen production	84
Figure 45. MVB growth from year 1 to year 10 of polyphenols extraction	85

Executive summary

This document presents the development of PILOT 1 in terms of technology and bioprocess optimization. Pilot 1 operated at SAV's bioprocess demonstrative facilities in Paiporta (Valencia) and was focused on the recovery of different high added value products through the valorization of by-products in a city context. ADM-Biopolis was in charge of laboratory optimisation and technology assessment for the bioprocesses' performance while SAV was in charge of the operativity of the processes at the demonstrative plant scale.

Pilot 1 demonstrated the establishment of new value chains for urban biowaste (i.e. SCGs and fish and meat by-products) utilization for the production of higher value purpose products (i.e. gelatine, hydrolyzed collagen, carotenoids, coffee oil and polyphenols) in a city context.

Spent coffee grounds were recovered from the HoReCa (Hotels, Restaurants and Cafes) sector through different restaurants located in Valencia (Spain) while fish and meat by-products were collected from local markets (MercaValencia) and retail companies.

For collagen and hydrolyzed collagen production, several trials of raw materials were tested until the raw material was better selected into fish skin. Afterwards, the process was escalated with batches of 500 kg of fish skin. The parameters such as raw material loading (10-30 w/v), NaOH concentration (2-4 w/w), temperature of thermal hydrolysis and time of reaction were optimized in order to achieve the maximum yield of gelatin production. The maximum yield obtained was 131.25 g gelatin per kg of fish by-product at 24% (w/w) loading, 0.7% (w/w) NaOH in chemical treatment and thermal treatment at 60°C and 3 hours. The yields were very close to those reported in the literature from lab assays. The meat by-products also showed their suitability. Once we moved on to animal skin subproducts, the collagen extraction was demonstrated.

Carotenoid (astaxanthin) production was optimized at semi-industrial scale. An alkaline pretreatment step to improve sugar release was optimized; in addition, different enzymatic hydrolysis trials have been performed in order to choose the best enzymatic cocktail and parameters (pH, temperature, dosage, time of reaction) at pilot scale. Combination of alkaline pretreatment (0,3 M, 10% (w/v) SCG loading at 60°C for 6 hours) and enzymatic hydrolysis using Celluclast 1.5 L and Xylanase 2X at 0,5% loading at milder conditions (55°C, pH 5) gave a yield of 5.14 g of glucose per liter. *Xanthophyllomyces dendrorhous* (formerly *Phaffia rhodozyma*) was selected for the astaxanthin production due that *Xanthophyllomyces dendrorhous* is considered by European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) to be suitable for the qualified presumption of safety (QPS) pre-assessment that covers safety concerns for humans, animals and the environment. Maximum yield of astaxanthin production achieved was 0.7 grams per kg of SCG.

Producing organic fertilizer from blood subproducts was also demonstrated at semi-industrial scale showing its viability and feasibility. The process involves a chemical hydrolysis of the animal blood.

Extraction of coffee oil was achieved with batches of 3Kg of dried SCGs. The solvent used for the extraction was n-hexane. The yield obtained was 14% w/w.

For the polyphenols extraction, the yield was 17.62 mg gallic acid equivalents per gram of SCG. The bioprocesses were optimized achieving an efficiency of the process of 95%, which demonstrates the feasibility of the process selected.

1. Introduction

1.1. Pilot overview and objectives

The main objective of Pilot 1 is to demonstrate the valorization of meat and fish by-products (wastes and unsold materials) and spent coffee grounds into high-added value products in a city context. At this point, the aim of the Pilot 1 is to demonstrate at large scale the production of gelatin, hydrolyzed collagen and organic fertilizer from meat and fish by-products; and carotenoids and oils and polyphenols from Spent Coffee Grounds (SCG). Another objective is to involve local stakeholders to reach the desired awareness in the collection and utilization of urban biowaste.

Pilot 1 is located in Valencia (Spain). Project activities were carried out in the Bioprocess Demonstrative Facility (BDF) of SAV, placed in Paiporta (Valencia). BDF is a new valorization plant built in SAV to develop R&D activities related to biowaste valorization, biotechnology and circular economy.

Feedstocks treated in the framework of WaysTUP! are SCG and meat and fish by-products. Meat by-products in this last period consisted of meat skin (*Oryctolagus cuniculus*) and slaughterhouse blood, and fish by-products consisted of skin, with punctual impurities of fins and heads. Both animal by-products are used to produce functional ingredients, such as gelatin, fertilizers and hydrolysed collagen. On the other side, SCG is utilized for the extraction of oils and polyphenols by solid/liquid solvent extraction and for the production of carotenoids through fermentation.

ADM-Biopolis S.L. (Paterna, Valencia) is the technological partner responsible for the development of treatment bioprocesses in Pilot 1. ADM-Biopolis has established all the experimental protocols to obtain the different bioproducts. For the bioprocess's optimization, different experiments have been performed at laboratory scale in ADM-Biopolis in order to obtain the maximum productivity and considering energy and water wastes. These protocols have been scale-up to demonstrative scale in SAV facilities and bioprocesses have also been optimized at BDF. SAV was in charge of the operativity of the processes at the demonstrative plant scale.

Table 1. Pilot 1 Overview

PILOT 1	
Place	Valencia
Responsible partner	SAV
Type of feedstock	Meat, fish and spent coffee ground
Feedstock provision	MercaValencia, markets, HoReCa
Processes	SCG: - Saccharification and fermentation - Extraction of oils and aromas Fish and meat: mechanical and chemical treatment
Responsible partner for process development	SAV (Technological support from Biopolis)
End-products	Carotenoids, oil, polyphenols, gelatin, hydrolysed collagen and hydrolysed blood
Responsible partner for end-product development	SAV (Technological support from Biopolis)

1.2. Bioprocess' description

1.1.1. Production of carotenoids from spent coffee ground (SCG)

Coffee is one of the most popular beverages in the world. The generation of solid residues from coffee beverage production, known as spent coffee grounds, is also a waste stream. It is estimated that 650 kg of SCG are generated from 1 ton of green coffee beans, thus around 6 million tons per year are produced worldwide. The majority of SCG is landfilled or combusted, involving a high risk to the environment, since this kind of disposal leads to the emission of greenhouse gasses, such as methane and carbon dioxide, contributing to the overall atmospheric pollution (Mayson and Williams, 2021). Coffee greenhouse gas emissions are measured at 16,50 kg CO₂ eq per kilogram of coffee. Regarding SCGs, 1 ton of SCG generates 682 kg of CO₂eq, while the landfilling of SCG produces 28.644 million tons of CO₂eq per year, a quantity comparable to the CO₂ generated by 10.6 million liters of burned diesel fuel (Mitraka et al., 2021).

In Pilot 1, SCG collected from the HoReCa sector are subjected to enzymatic hydrolysis in order to break lignocellulosic structure and release polysaccharides and nutrients from the raw material. The coffee hydrolysate is used as a nutrient source in the fermentation carried out by the yeast *Xanthophyllomyces dendrorhous*. During fermentation, yeast produces carotenoids within the route of their metabolism. The major carotenoid produced by this yeast is astaxanthin. For comparison, we have also tested one of the most popular yeast for producing carotenoids, *Sporobolomyces roseus* and we show the results in the next paragraphs.

Table 2. Chemical composition of spent coffee ground (Ballesteros et al., 2014; Obruca et al., 2015; Perta-Crisan et al., 2019).

Component	weight %
Cellulose	7-12
Hemicellulose	30-40
Arabinose	3-4
Mannose	16-20
Galactose	11-16
Lignin	25-30
Oil	10-20
Proteins	10-18

1.1.2. Extraction of oils and polyphenols from SCGs

For the extraction of oils from spent coffee grounds, different methods are proposed, such as Soxhlet (solid-liquid extraction methodologies, in pilot 1) and supercritical fluid extraction (pilot 2). For Soxhlet extraction, n-hexane, diethyl ether or other organic solvents are used under reflux, giving 10-20% oil yield. The main limitation of this method is the use of volatile organic solvents, which are harmful towards the environment and human health and the difficulties to scale-up the process (Karmee, 2018).

The extraction of antioxidants from SCG can be carried out applying different methods, such as solid-liquid extraction using aqueous alcohol solution (methanol, ethanol and isopropanol) (Mata et al., 2018), water, or by pressurized liquid extraction (PLE) method with water and ethanol (Shang et al., 2017; Perta-Crisan et al., 2019).

In Pilot 1, SCG collected from the HoReCa sector are subjected to solid/liquid treatment for the extraction of oils and polyphenols. Soxhlet extraction with n-hexane is the chosen method to extract oils from SCG, while polyphenols are extracted by using 70% (v/v) ethanol. After solid/liquid extraction, the liquid fraction is subjected to distillation in a rotary evaporator to recover the bioproducts and recycle the solvent.

1.1.3. Production of gelatin and active peptides from meat and fish by-products

The food industry produces a large amount of waste, which is divided according to its origin into animal and vegetable by-products. In the slaughter of animals, the waste represents approximately 35% of the animal's live weight, while industrial fish filleting represents a considerably wasteful practice, yielding only between 30 to 50% of muscle. Secondary animal

by-products originate from various processing sectors of the food industry (Mokrejš et al., 2021; Valcarcel et al., 2021).

Most of these by-products can be a highly valuable raw material resource. By-products are rich in natural polymers, e.g., chicken heads, stomachs or paws contain 50–75% protein in dry matter (made up of 83–98% collagen). By suitable processing technologies, unused parts of animal bodies can be processed into usable products. Some protein by-products, especially those that contain collagen, are further utilized. The most frequently processed are skins and bones, which are used primarily to produce gelatins and collagen hydrolysates, which are widely used, especially in the production of food, food supplements or cosmetics (Mokrejš et al., 2021).

Pilot 1 demonstrates the production of gelatin and active peptides from fish and meat by-products in a multi-step process involving the following key operations: crushing, conditioning, hot-water extraction, concentration and drying. Each step will be further explained in section 2.2.

1.3. Bioproducts and potential applications

1.3.1. Carotenoids

Carotenoids is a generic term used to designate most pigments naturally found in animal and plant kingdoms and comprises more than 700 compounds responsible for the red, orange and yellow colors. Most carotenoids are tetraterpenoids, consisting of highly unsaturated isoprene derivatives. They act as membrane-protective antioxidants. All photosynthetic organisms (including plants, algae and cyanobacteria) and some non-photosynthetic bacteria and fungi synthesize carotenoids. Due to their coloring properties, carotenoids are often used in food, pharmaceutical, cosmetics and animal feed industries (Petrik et al., 2014; Mezzomo and Ferreira, 2016).

Biotechnological production of carotenoids can be industrially feasible if process costs are reduced by using cheap carbon substrates from food or agriculture wastes, such as spent coffee grounds. One of carotenoids more used in food and feed industries that can be produced through biotechnology is astaxanthin (Petrik et al., 2014).

Astaxanthin is an orange-pink carotenoid pigment commonly found in marine animals. It has a strong antioxidant activity and some essential biological functions, including protection against UV-light effects and enhancing immune response. Astaxanthin has numerous applications in various sectors, including food, feed, and nutraceutical industries, since some farm animals, like salmonids, usually use this carotenoid to enhance orange color and to improve growth and survival. Until now, production of astaxanthin is carried out by chemical

synthesis, but there are some microorganisms capable of synthesizing high levels of astaxanthin that can be used for the commercial bioproduction of this carotenoid. These microorganisms include the green microalgae *Haematococcus pluvialis* and the yeast *Xanthophyllomyces dendrorhous* (Hu et al., 2007; Jirasripongpun et al., 2007).

1.3.2. Oils and polyphenols

Oils and fats are the most abundant lipids in nature. Fats and oils are called triglycerides because they are esters composed of three fatty acid units joined to glycerol. Oils are composed of mainly unsaturated fatty acids which will take a liquid form at room temperature while fats are composed of high amounts of saturated fatty acids which will take a solid form at room temperature.

Oil extracted from coffee has a potential use for cosmetic applications due to its emollient and anti-ageing properties (Wagemaker et al., 2015). The oil extracted from unroasted coffee beans is known as green coffee oil (GCO). The major compounds of GCO are fatty acids, mainly linoleic and palmitic acids (Wagemaker et al., 2011). Studies show that GCO contributes to the skin barrier and improves hydration (Patzelt et al., 2012). Some studies have also demonstrated the capacity of GCO to absorb UVB radiation (Wagemaker et al., 2015; Wagemaker et al., 2011). Furthermore, coffee oil has naturally high content of antioxidants which makes the oil very stable since this helps to not decompose very quickly (Al-Hamamre et al. 2012).

Another application for coffee oil is in biodiesel production since this oil remains viscous and does not congeal given its relatively low levels of saponified matter (Al-Hamamre et al. 2012).

The oil content in the coffee varies from 11 to 20 wt% depending on the type (Daglia, M., 2004). In spent coffee grounds, the oil content ranges from 10% to 15 wt% (Al-Hamamre et al. 2012).

Polyphenols are a large family of natural organic compounds characterized by containing multiple phenol and hydroxyl units. Polyphenols are secondary metabolites that are common in plants. Polyphenols have received attention among nutritionists, food scientists and consumers since they can have strong antioxidant properties against oxidative stress caused by excess reactive oxygen species (Tsao 2010). Polyphenols in coffee contribute a lot to its flavor (Wang et al. 2009). Studies have found that coffee polyphenols, such as chlorogenic acids, have many health benefits (Yamagata, K. 2018).

1.3.3. Gelatin and active peptides

Gelatin is one of the most important products obtained from meat and fish by-products; it is a heterogeneous mixture of peptides derived from collagen, and it is obtained by the destruction of cross-linkages between the polypeptide chains and some breakage of polypeptide bonds. Thus, collagen is the most abundant structural protein in both vertebrates

and invertebrates and constitutes approximately 30% of animal's total proteins. Further extensive enzymatic degradation of gelatin results in gelatin hydrolysates, being considered active peptides (Liu et al., 2015).

Gelatin and gelatin-derived active peptides have been studied for their potential biological benefits, such as antioxidant, antihypertensive, anticancer, anti-photoaging and cholesterol-lowering effects (Liu et al., 2015). Because of their good properties, they are widely used in the food, pharmaceutical, cosmetic, biomedical materials and leather industries (Duan et al., 2009). Compared with mammalian gelatins, fish gelatins have a lower content of amino acids (Pro and Hyp), which weakens their structural stability and rheological behaviors and lowers their melting temperature and gel strength, being more suitable for the preparation of bioactive peptides because they are more easily hydrolyzed (Qiu et al., 2019).

The conventional food, photographic, cosmetic and pharmaceutical application of gelatin is based mainly on its gel-forming and viscoelastic properties. Currently, especially in food industry, gelatin has many applications in products such as emulsifiers, foaming agents, colloid stabilizers, fining agents, biodegradable packaging materials and microencapsulating agents, in line with the growing trend to replace synthetic agents with more natural ones (Gómez-Guillén et al., 2011).

Moreover, collagen and gelatin-derived peptides have exhibited numerous other bioactivities: antimicrobial activity, mineral binding capacity, the lipid-lowering effect, immunomodulatory activity and beneficial effects on skin, bone or joint health (Gómez-Guillén et al., 2011).

1.3.4. Organic fertilizers

Soils are finite natural resources with critical socio-economic and ecological functions, including food production (95% depends on soil), biodiversity conservation (25% hosted by soils), and regulation of water supplies (FAO 2022. Where Food Begins). Today 60-70% of soils are degraded across the EU due to unsustainable soil exploitation and the disproportionate use of synthetic chemicals (European Commission. Caring for Soil is Caring for Life. (2020).).

Nowadays a product with the potential to solve this soil problem is needed. Here is where the blood has its niche. The animal's blood is a major by-product from slaughterhouses. The upgrading of these by-products solves the problem of their disposal as blood is the major pollutant from slaughterhouse waters, Blood is composed of water, organic matter, and inorganic matter (NPK). Dried and milled blood from slaughterhouses, frequently used as an organic fertilizer and it has high N (13.2%) and Fe content able to enhance plant growth in soils. A mixture of disrupted protein from animal blood, rich in peptides and amino acids will be obtained.

1.4.State of the art of the biowaste valorization

1.4.1. Spent Coffee Grounds valorization

The spent coffee waste contains large amounts of organic compounds (i.e. fatty acids, lignin, cellulose, hemicellulose, and other polysaccharides) that justify its valorization. Some researchers have investigated spent coffee waste as a bioresource for various valuable compounds. Thereby, coffee residue has been investigated for biodiesel production, as source of sugars, as precursor for production of activated carbon, as compost, and as sorbent for metal ion removal (Pujol et al., 2013).

One of the most remarkable utilizations of SCG is energy production, since it can be used as biomass due to its high organic content. SCG also represents a renewable source of fuel production (bio-oil, biodiesel, bioethanol, pellets, etc.).

SCG chemical composition includes significant amounts of lipids (10-20 %w/w), which could be used as feedstock in biodiesel production. For the extraction of oils from spent coffee grounds, several methods have been proposed, such as Soxhlet and supercritical fluid extraction (Karmee, 2018). After oil extraction, a transesterification step is necessary for biodiesel production. On the other hand, besides biodiesel production, numerous microorganisms can use oil extracted from SCGs as a carbon source to obtain valuable products. The most common type of biopolymers produced using SCG are polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA), which are natural polyesters of 3-,4-, 5-, and 6-hydroxyalkanoic acids, that are synthesized by microorganisms for storing energy, and are considered as a biodegradable and biocompatible alternative to petrochemical plastics (Giroto et al., 2017; Kovalcik et al., 2018; Garcia and Kim, 2021).

SCG are also a source of recoverable sugars, especially cellulose and hemicellulose, which are generally extracted by hydrolysis. One of the most common options is enzymatic hydrolysis to obtain monosaccharides such as glucose, mannose, arabinose or galactose. Several cellulolytic and hemicellulolytic microorganisms can be applied for enzymatic hydrolysis and some of the most efficient hydrolytic enzymes are mannanases and cellulases (Obruca et al., 2014; Wang et al., 2016; Kovalcik et al., 2018). Afterwards, the hydrolysate can be used as a nutrient in fermentation using yeast *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* to produce bioethanol. Therefore, bioethanol produced can be converted into bioethers in order to be used as fuel additives in several countries, such as France, the Netherlands, Germany, Spain and Belgium (Karmee, 2018).

1.4.2. Meat and fish by-products valorization

It is estimated that around 88 million tons of food is wasted in Europe every year. Most studies focusing on measuring food waste in the EU agree that the largest share of food is wasted at the consumption stage, followed by the processing stage. According to a recent work

published by Caldeira et al., (2019), the total food waste generated at the processing stage was found to be 30,6 million tons annually, being five sub-sectors the main contributors: 35% of waste corresponds to fruits, vegetables, tubers; 33% to oil crops; 20% to meat, fish and poultry; 8% to cereal grains; and 4% to dairy products (Rao et al., 2021).

Industrial fish and meat processing generate huge amounts of wastes, since about 40-60% of the total weight of animals and fishes are classified as residuals. This includes heads, bones, carcasses, blood, skin, viscera, hooves and feathers, depending on the species. These wastes are important protein sources and contain essential aminoacids, minerals and vitamins, so they have a great potential for higher-value applications in food and feed, besides the production of gelatin and active peptides (Aspevik et al., 2017).

On one hand, meat by-products can offer various compounds with technological applications in the food industry. Immunoglobulins, serum albumin and fibrinogen are used for their gelation and emulsification properties. Plasma proteins can be used for protein enrichment and foaming. The combination of enzymes thrombin and fibrinogen (Fibrimex[®]) is used for binding meat pieces and for increasing the hardness of meat products (Rao et al., 2021).

On the other hand, it is estimated that around 25-35% of fish by-products are used as materials to produce fishmeal and fish oil (FAO, 2020). There are alternative processes to valorize fish discards and produce fish mince, gelatins, oils and fish protein hydrolysates to be used as aquaculture feed ingredients. Wastes generated from the industrial processing of various fish species can also be turned into peptones (Rudovica et al., 2021).

2. Methodology

2.1. Logistics for biowaste collection

2.1.1. Spent Coffee Grounds

Spent coffee grounds are recovered from different restaurants located in Valencia (Spain) through a collection system where these establishments are provided with containers designed for the project (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Container designed for the collection of SCG.

A SAV logistics team is in charge of distributing these containers to some restaurants in the city of Valencia. These restaurants collect all the spent coffee grounds in the containers generated for four days; during these few days, each restaurant can collect about 5 or 6 kg of SCG. Afterwards, SAV logistics team collects coffee waste from restaurants through a collecting system, where the destination is the Bioprocess Demonstrative Facility (BDF) of SAV. This procedure is carried out every two weeks (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Spent coffee ground collection system developed in the city of Valencia. From restaurants to the Bioprocess Demonstrative Facility of SAV.

2.1.2. Fish by-products

For the logistics of fish by-products (Figure 3), at the beginning of the demonstration phase, raw material was collected from Mercavalencia with a SAV logistics team. However, Pilot 1 faced some problems related to feedstock supply from Mercavalencia because of the size of the by-products and the incapacity of treat them in the pilot plant, so new fish by-products providers were sought, such as municipal markets and other local companies. SAV receives around 1 tn weekly from Mercavalencia and other fish retail companies. They are kept in industrial freezers at very low temperatures, between -14 and -18 °C, until SAV collection using 240 L plastic containers. From the quantity received every week, a selection of fish parts of interest is made. From the whole fish by-product from Mercavalencia, skins, heads and bones are selected, while the other parts are discarded, since they do not contain enough collagen.

Figure 3. Logistics for fish by-products collection

Therefore, logistics is also being optimized, as more sources of fish by-products have been obtained from other fish companies. Currently, we are also collaborating with two retail companies that provide us only with salmon by-products, which includes bones, heads and skins. Salmon by-products (Figure 4), compared to the fish by-products from Mercavalencia (tuna, swordfish, monkfish or mackerels), have shown to be more suitable for gelatine extraction than the rest of fish by-products previously treated.

Figure 4. 1 tn of salmon by-products received for gelatine and hydrolyzed collagen production.

Feedstock related challenges

Due to the exceptional global situation, SAV, as many other partners, have faced special situations that differ with the designed usual route map. To record the most important ones, that have been sorted successfully:

- The original raw material in the very first trials was in an optimum calibre. Fishes such as mackerel and anchovy were used. When the first trials with real volume quantities started, we discovered that the size of mackerel, anchovy, and others was not the usual, and fishes much larger entered to the Mercavalencia waste stream, such as tuna, swordfish and snuff (Figure 5). Due to the dimension of our grinder, those calibre of raw material were not optimum.
- This obstacle derived in two situations. First of all, we tried to force the grinder, by separating from tuna heads, ribs and column all the possible usable raw material, while in the second place we started searching for other source providers and/or sea waste raw material at the same time, so that whenever Mercavalencia could not provide small pieces we had alternatives.

Figure 5. Pictures of large fish by-products received.

- We tried cephalopod residue, very abundant in the Comunitat Valenciana. Although the collagen content in bibliography says it has good percentages, our process does not fit it specially well and the analytics arose 2.4% of collagen, a very poor performance.
- At process level, some equipment broke and we had to do an early maintenance. The steam generator broke down for one month, and two more weeks for the air compressor, two of the most important equipment.
- Transport constrictions delayed the supply of some reagents, and the last transport strike suffered at Spain also some fish deliveries.

2.1.3. Meat by-products

For the logistics of meat by-products, Mercavalencia was also considered the main provider, since during the preparation of Pilot 1, some of the by-products generated in their slaughterhouse, mainly pig skins and carcasses, were suitable for the extraction of gelatine and active peptides. So, the logistics was the same as the one designed for the fish by-products i.e., preservation in Mercavalencia at very low temperatures and collection by SAV logistics team in 240 L plastic containers. However, when the demonstration phase started and large quantities of this type of materials were required, the availability was very limited and the possibilities of performing a bioprocess were scarce. Moreover, meat market is very competitive, nearly every part of the animals is sold for food or feed, and some of the category 3 by-products, such as pigs or other mammals' skins already have a defined market and they are also sold by the slaughterhouses.

As a result, the solid meat by-products mostly available in Mercavalencia were composed of bones that are not suitable to be treated in our demo facility, which was designed for the production of active peptides and enzymes from "soft" raw materials, such as skins, carcasses

or meat trimmings. Therefore, even if they could be processed in our demo plant, the treatment of bones would take much longer than the already planned (from 3-5h to 20-24h) for the bioprocess, making it techno-economically unfeasible.

In order to overcome these challenges, other slaughterhouses were contacted as new meat by-products suppliers and, as a result, two different feedstocks were treated for the production of gelatine and active peptides: blood and rabbit skin. On the one hand, Mercavalencia continued as meat by-product supplier, but in this case it was the provider of the liquid meat by-product: the blood. Blood contains a high concentration of protein that ranges from 12 to 18% of its total content, which translates into 120-180 grams of protein per liter of blood. This high protein content makes blood a great candidate for the production of enzymes and active peptides.

On the other hand, the other two slaughterhouses were the suppliers of rabbit skin (Figure 6), a meat by-product with high availability and low valorisation routes in Spain. The rabbit skin contains approximately a 15% of protein, which makes it also a perfect candidate for the obtention of gelatine and active peptides for the production of functional ingredients.

Figure 6. Rabbit dried skin as feedstock for the production of enzymes and active peptides.

2.2. Feedstock characterization

The composition of feedstocks used in the different biotechnological processes was analyzed. The most important parameters analyzed were total solids, fat content, total proteins and carbohydrates.

Working protocols developed to determine the structural composition for meat and fish were as follows.

2.2.1. Determination of Total Solids

Before starting the analysis, it is necessary to determine the amount of moisture present in the sample, since the calculations are always made on a dry basis. The determination of total solids

is carried out by dry weight. Approximately 2 g of substrate are weighed in aluminum trays previously dried in an oven at 105°C and cooled in a desiccator. The trays are weighed (P1), tared and the wet substrate weighed on them (P0). Samples are dried at 105°C for a minimum of 20 hours, cooled in a desiccator and weighed (P2).

Total solids = $((P2-P1)/P0) \times 100$

2.2.2. Extraction of fats

The extraction of fats was performed in the Soxhlet extractor on 10 g of standard substrate with 500 mL chloroform in a cellulose cartridge. The bath is set at 85°C and the extraction is carried out for a minimum of 2 hours or until no coloration is observed on the collector. An attempt is made to remove from the water bath as soon as the system has finished siphoning.

After extraction, the cellulose cartridge is placed in a glass beaker and left in the hood until all the solvent has evaporated. Once virtually free of solvent, the contents of the cartridge are poured into a clean, dry, tared beaker. The fat-free substrate is dried at 75 °C in the oven overnight (O/N) and weighed to calculate the fat content of the sample by difference (Pérez-Palacios *et al.*, 2008).

2.2.3. Monounsaturated and polyunsaturated fat content

The method involves a hydrolysis/ether extraction of fat followed by quantitative GC analysis versus an internal standard (House, 1997).

2.2.4. Protein analysis

Protein content is measured by Kjeldahl method (Barbano *et al.*, 1990).

2.2.5. Carbohydrates content analysis

Carbohydrate analysis is performed by HPLC using amino-bonded reversed-phase columns (Karkacier *et al.*, 2003).

2.3. Bioprocess steps and equipment

2.3.1. Carotenoids production from Spent Coffee Grounds through fermentation

For the production of carotenoids from SCG (Figure 7), a first enzymatic hydrolysis step for sugars and nutrients extraction from raw material is needed. Enzymatic hydrolysis is carried out in a 500 L heated reactor during 48h at 55°C, pH 5. Cellulolytic enzymes are added in a concentration of 0.5-2% (v/v) and SCG loading varies from 10 to 20% (w/v). Enzymatic digestion is used to break up cellulose releasing fermentable saccharides.

Figure 7. Bioprocess diagram for the carotenoids production.

Coffee hydrolysate, plenty of sugars and nutrients, is used as substrate in the next fermentation step. Fermentation is developed in a 100 L heated bioreactor, which can measure and control temperature, agitation, aeration, pH and dissolved oxygen. For temperature, the system has a Pt-100 temperature sensor and a PID controller. For stirring, the control unit has a rotor connected to the reactor turbines, which maintains the previously set agitation by means of a PID controller. Measurement of pH is carried out with a Hamilton sensor, while this variable is controlled by a PID controller that acts on two peristaltic pumps for feeding acid and base.

During fermentation, coffee hydrolysate is used as a carbon and nutrient source for yeast growth. The yeast *Xanthophyllomyces dendrorhous* is the one used for carotenoids production, specifically for astaxanthin production. Different experiments have been developed to bioprocess optimization by the modification of temperature, time of reaction, stirring, inoculum loading % (v/v), coffee hydrolysate loading % (v/v) and pH.

Pre-inoculum is prepared by ADM-Biopolis growing *X. dendrorhous* in potato dextrose broth during 5-7 days at 25°C in orbital shaking.

After fermentation, cell biomass, containing the carotenoids, is separated by filtration in a tangential flow filtration (TFF) unit and then is concentrated to 1:9 ratio. Concentrated cell biomass is lysate using a PONY homogenizer. In the homogenizer, two pneumatic pistons exert high pressure (800-1000 bar) on the permeate and thus carry out cell lysis. At these high pressures, yeast cells are lysate and carotenoids are released to the culture medium.

Figure 8. Equipment used for the carotenoid production. From left to right: hydrolysis reactor, fermenter, tangential flow filtration (TFF) and homogenizer.

Figure 9. Carotenoids product after PONY homogenization

2.3.2. Extraction of oils and polyphenols from Spent Coffee Grounds

For the extraction of oils and polyphenols, two main components are needed: the solid-liquid extraction system (Soxhlet) and the rotavapor for liquid-liquid separation (Figure 10).

Figure 10. Bioprocess diagram for the oils and polyphenols extraction.

The process of extraction starts in the Soxhlet equipment (Figure 11). The solvent is introduced into the main flask (40 L) and brought to boil under vacuum, while the spent coffee grounds are introduced into the solid tank. Once the solvent vapors are condensed in the head, the pure solvent will circulate at the bottom of the flask with the solid product to be extracted. In the solid container, the solid-liquid extraction takes place, exiting by lateral overflow towards the bottom of the column generating a recirculation by natural convection. These evaporation and condensation cycles are carried out during 9h at the boiling temperature of the solvent under vacuum.

Figure 11. Solid-liquid extraction of oils and polyphenols from SCG in pilot Soxhlet equipment.

Depending on the extracted product from the spent coffee grounds, different solvents are used: ethanol 70% (v/v) or water to obtain polyphenols and n-hexane for oil extraction.

At the final Soxhlet step, two end-products are obtained because of solid-liquid extraction: the exhausted coffee (solid fraction) and the pure oil or polyphenols with each solvent. That liquid phase goes to the Rotavapor. During this operation, oils and polyphenols are concentrated through solvent distillation for 5 hours, obtaining as final products oils and polyphenols and on the other hand the solvent is recycled.

2.3.3. Production of gelatine and active peptides from fish and meat by-products

For the production of gelatin from fish and meat by-products, 10 stages are necessary to obtain it as a dry solid (Figure 16).

Stage 1: grinding of the fish and meat by-product is carried out with a grinder to obtain a suitable consistency in our raw material, thus breaking its structure and allowing the proteins to be extracted more quickly and easily (Figure 12).

Stage 2: the ground raw material is put into a tank in different loadings (10-30 % w/v), with the addition of NaOH (0.5-4% w/w). This chemical treatment is carried out at room temperature and with agitation so that the solid does not settle at the bottom of the tank.

Figure 12. Salmon by-products (left) and product after crushed (right).

Figure 13. Solid remains after the maceration and rotary sieve that will enter in the extraction tank.

Stage 4: the extraction is carried out in the reactor; this is the stage where the proteins are released. The solid-liquid ratio is the same as in stage 2 again with water, at a temperature of 75° C for 4 hours and with agitation.

Figure 14. Maceration process in 1,5 m3 tank.

Stage 5: the product goes through the rotary sieve again. Within the liquid part of the mixture, the proteins are suspended. On the other hand, the solid remainder obtained after passing through the rotary sieve is sent to Pilot 3 (insect protein).

Stage 6: the liquid part with the suspended proteins is passed through the filter press to clean the liquid of remaining solids (Figure 15). This filter is achieved through the filter cloths of the equipment and the earths that are previously added to the product to leave a precoat on the equipment, as well as other earths that are added to the product itself.

Figure 15. Filter press cloth after the separation of remaining solids.

Stage 7: the product now passes through a centrifugal separator. In this stage, the objective is to separate the product by density. In this way, the unwanted part of the oil is removed. The equipment performs a centrifugal force in a rotor, due to its rotation speed, pushing the product towards the walls through a disc in the central part that performs the separation depending on its diameter size (in such a way, the wider the disc is, the smaller portion of the less dense solution is separated).

Figure 16. Bioprocess diagram for the gelatin and hydrolyzed collagen production from fish and meat by-products.

Stage 8: ultrafiltration is performed on the UF-NF equipment through cartridges that perform a molecular cleavage of 10 kDa. In this way, the gelatin is separated from the rest of the components with bigger size as the rest of fibers, particles, etc.

Stage 9: finally, the gelatin is dried in a rotary drum dryer (Figure 17). The first step is to heat the rotary drum dryer with water steam, this drum is in constant movement making uniform the heating at the surface. Once the equipment is at the right temperature (<130 °C), the gelatin is applied to the drum with a roller that adheres a layer to the drum with a uniform thickness in this way.

Figure 17. Gelatine drying at the SAV's drum dryer.

As the drum rotates the gelatin dries until it reaches a blade that separates the powdered gelatin from the drum.

Stage 10: once the gelatin is powdered, it is passed through the grinded rotor mill to refine the gelatin grain.

In the case of obtaining hydrolyzed collagen and active peptides from solid meat and fish by-products, the process consists of thirteen stages.

The bioprocess is the same until stage 8 in which ultrafiltration is carried out, separating the gelatin from the rest of the proteins.

Stage 9: enzymatic hydrolysis is carried out in the 500 L reactor with the product retained after the ultrafiltration, adjusting the pH to 8 with NaOH and incubating at a temperature of 50 °C for 4 hours. After hydrolysis, the enzyme is inactivated at 90 °C for 30 minutes. In this way, active peptides are obtained.

Step 10: the nanofiltration step is carried out in the UF-NF equipment. Through cartridges that perform a molecular separation of 200 Da. In this separation, the peptides remain in the product retained in the equipment, with the rest of the gelatin passing into the permeate.

Stage 11: the product retained in the nanofiltration is introduced into the buffer tank of the flash evaporator to remove water and concentrate the sample. In this equipment, the product is heated through a heat exchanger until it reaches a working temperature between 85 and

100 °C. It reaches the evaporator by flashing at a temperature of 140 °C. It then passes through another cold exchanger and returns to the buffer tank. Depending on the desirable concentration, different passes through the flash evaporator are made.

Stage 12: once the product is concentrated, it goes to the rotary drum dryer. The process is the same as in stage 9 for obtaining gelatin. In this way the dry peptide powder is obtained.

Stage 13: finally, as in stage 10, the product is passed through the rotary mill to refine the grain.

On the other hand, the production of active peptides from liquid meat by-products (animal's blood) has required the design of another bioprocess (Figure 18), but using the equipment already acquired.

The first step includes a previous filtration with a metallic strainer in order to remove some impurities that can interfere with the process, such as hair and small stones. Afterwards, a mechanical homogenization at 600 bar takes place to break physically erythrocyte cell membranes for intercellular material release, which is rich in hemoglobin.

Figure 18. Bioprocess diagram for the production of enzymes and active peptides from blood

Once the blood has been homogenized, the entire liquid is subjected to chemical hydrolysis. During chemical hydrolysis using NaOH 2% (w/v) for the chemical hydrolysis at 60°C for 3–6h, protein chains are broken and enzymes, active peptides and free amino acids are released. In this case, all the raw material becomes the final product.

2.4. Pilot scale trials

2.4.1. Production of carotenoids from SCGs

For the optimization of carotenoid production from SCG, several trials were performed.

First step of this bioprocess is the subjection of SCG to enzymatic hydrolysis, where several enzymes and conditions have been tested.

For this step, an enzymatic screening was conducted at laboratory scale (BIOPOLIS) in order to determine the best enzymes and conditions to carry out the bioprocess. During these trials, different enzymes: Celluclast 1.5 L, Vinotaste Pro, Ultraflo and Viscozyme have been used at different conditions for temperature, pH, concentration and time of reaction. Results of these trials will be shown in section 3.2.1.

At large scale, initial enzymatic hydrolysis was also carried out in order to determine the best enzymes to develop the treatment (Table 3), using parameters according to the enzyme's technical sheets.

Table 3. Initial enzymatic hydrolysis trials through enzymatic screening

Enzyme	Enzyme Concentration % (v/v)	SCG loading % (w/v)	pH	Temperature (° C)	Time (h)
Celluclast 1.5 L	0.0625	10	4,5	50	48
Celluclast 1.5 L	0.0625	10	5	50	48
Celluclast 1.5 L	0.0625	10	5	60	48
Vinotaste	0.0625	10	3	40	48
Vinotaste	0.0625	10	5	50	48
Vinotaste	0.0625	10	3	60	48
Ultraflo	0.0625	10	5	50	48
Ultraflo	0.0625	10	5	70	48
Viscozyme	0.0625	10	5	40	48
Viscozyme	0.0625	10	5	50	48
Viscozyme	0.0625	10	5	60	48

After the initial trials at pilot scale, two enzymes Celluclast 1.5 L (Enzyme 1 - E1) and Vinotaste Pro (Enzyme 2 - E2) were selected to carry out more experiments during 48 h at 50 °C (

Table 4).

Table 4. Enzymatic hydrolysis tests using Celluclast 1.5 L (E1) and Vinotaste Pro (E2) at different concentrations

Trial	E1 % (v/v)	E2 % (w/v)	SCG loading % (w/v)
H1	0.06	0.06	10
H2	0.20	0.20	20
H3	0.50	0.50	10

Since the sugar yield after enzymatic hydrolysis was not very high (Table 19), more experiments adding an alkaline pretreatment were performed. SCG is a lignocellulosic waste stream and lignin in its structural form inhibits cellulolytic enzyme activity. Thus, a pretreatment step aiming to improve efficiency of enzymes was eventually added.

Among the different pretreatment methods, the alkaline was adopted since NaOH solutions are applied under milder conditions, have lower pollution impact, are less corrosive than acids and are very efficient to lignocellulosic materials with low lignin content (Valles et al., 2021). Thus, more experiments considering the addition of NaOH in a pretreatment step have been designed varying NaOH concentration (0.3M, 0.5M and 0.7M), temperature (60, 70, 80 °C) and time (2, 4 or 6 h). One initial trial was developed with NaOH 0.3M, 10% (w/v) loading SCG at 60°C for 6 hours. After the pretreatment step, pH was adjusted to 5 by using H₂SO₄ 4M and 0,5% (v/v) of Celluclast 1.5 L were added. Enzymatic hydrolysis was developed for 72h at 50°C.

After enzymatic hydrolysis, hydrolysate is used as a substrate in the fermentation for the production of carotenoids. Several experiments were performed in order to optimize the operational parameters of the fermentation. Table 5 shows the different tests. Once the homogenization process is finished, the resulting volume is sent to ADM-WILD for carotenoids characterization and purification.

Table 5. Parameters conditions for the production of carotenoids. Bioprocess's steps and different tests.

Parameters	Car-1	Car-2	Car-3	Car-4	Car-5	Car-6
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ENZYMATIC HYDROLYSIS	Hydrolysate	H-1	H-2	H-2	H-2	H-3	H-3
FERMENTATION	Temperature (°C)	25	20	20	20	20	20
	pH	5	5	5	5	5	5
	Total volume (L)	80	40	60	60	40	40
	Agitation (rpm)	300	500	500	500	500	500
	Aeration (vvm)	0,5	0,5	0,5	1	1	1
	Time (h)	48	72	72	72	100	72
	Hydrolysate % (v/v)	20	10	10	13	20	10
TFF	Inoculum % (v/v)	5	5	5	5	5	6,25
	Initial volume (L)	-	40	60	60	40	40
	Time (min)	-	30	30	90	120	150
	Pressure (bar)	-	4-6	4-6	2	2	2
PONY HOMOGENIZATION	Final volume (L)	-	10	12	8,5	8,5	7
	Passes	-	5	5	8	6	7
	Pressure (bar)	-	350-500	800	800	800	1000

2.4.2. Extraction of oils and polyphenols from SCG

The extraction of oil from dried coffee grounds is performed in the Soxhlet apparatus with hexane as solvent.

The boiling temperature of the hexane at atmospheric pressure is 69°C while under appropriate vacuum conditions, the boiling point drops to 40°C. The evaporated hexane condenses on reaching the cold coil, and the liquid fills the flask containing the sample. The hexane comes into contact with the coffee and starts to release soluble compounds in this solvent. This process is carried out for 8 hours. The resulting sample is subjected to evaporation at a rotary evaporator, separating the solvent, hexane, from the oil extracted from the coffee.

The initial results of oil yield obtained was 13-16% of the initial substrate weight.

The extraction of polyphenols from dried coffee grounds is performed in Soxhlet with 70% ethanol or water as solvent. The boiling temperature of ethanol at atmospheric pressure is 78°C while under appropriate vacuum conditions, the boiling point drops to 50°C. The solvent comes into contact with the coffee and starts to release polyphenolic compounds. The extracted sample volume is subjected to evaporation for concentration.

From the initial trials, a maximum yield of 8.26 mg gallic acid equivalents per gram of SCG using water as solvent at a ratio substrate/solvent of 1/20.

2.4.3. Production of gelatin from fish by-products

For the production of gelatin from fish by-products, various tests have been performed, where parameters of chemical treatment and thermal hydrolysis were modified in order to optimize the bioprocess. Processes were carried out in large scale (1.5 m³ tanks) as described in the section 2.3.3.

Table 6. Trials and steps for the production of gelatin from fish by-products. Muscle meat and viscera of multiple big fishes (MMV); small fishes (SM); salmon heads, bones and skins (SHBS).

Test	P-0	P-1	P-2	P-3	P-4	P-5	P-6	P-7
Feedstock composition	MMV	MMV	MMV	SM	SHBS	SHBS	SHBS	SHBS
Chemical Treatment								
Duration (h)	20	18	24	20	23	16	21	15
Temperature (°c)	Room	Room	Room	Room	Room	Room	Room	Room
Stirring	4	4-5	4-5	4	4	4	4	3
Fish (%)	15	9	9	21	20	27.6	20	30
NaOH %(w/w)	2	3	3	1.89	2	2	2	0
Thermal Extraction								
Duration (h)	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	16
Temperature (°C)	75	75	75	75	75	75	75	75
Stirring (Level)	4	4-5	4-5	4	4	4	4	4
Fish (%)	12	6	7	-	11	25	10	28.3
Exhausted Solid (%)	0.3	0.3	0.0	-	0.0	0.0	0.8	1.1
Press filtration								
Soil pre-layer (ratio kg/100 L)	0.68	1.023	1.023	-	0.625	0.625	0.625	1.023

Ratio (kg/m ²)	0.50	0.75	0.75	-	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.75
Soil in product (kg/100L)	0.25	0.25	0.25	-	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25
Ratio	5:1	5:1	5:1	-	5:1	5:1	5:1	5:1
Duration (min)	90	90	90	-	60	60	60	90
Centrifugation								
Duration (h)	-	-	-	-	1	1	1.5	2
Volume (L)	-	-	-	-	250	170	500	600
Stirring (rpm)	-	-	-	-	12000	12000	12000	12000
Flow rate (L/h)	-	-	-	-	300	150	350	350
°Brix inlet	-	-	-	-	-	4	-	3

In addition to the chemical and thermal optimization, other steps of the bioprocesses are being optimized. Because of that, different initial trials were performed in the filter press to adapt the layer and pre-layer for the correct removal of suspended particles from the hydrolysis medium. Tests to the pre-layer formation using different dosages of Celite 545[®] were done (Table 7).

Table 7. Pre-layer formation tests using different dosages of Celite 545[®]

Test code	Ratio	Celite 545 (kg)	Water volume (L)	Pressure (bar)
1.1	0.5 kg/m ²	0.68	100	180-200
1.2	0.75 kg/m ²	1.023	100	180-200
1.3	1 kg/m ²	1.364	100	180-200

Moreover, for the layer formation on the filter press, other experiments were done by adding Celite Hyflo Super-Cel at different concentrations to the volume of hydrolysate (Table 8).

Table 8. Layer formation tests using different dosages of Celite Hyflo Super-Cel

Test code	Ratio	Celite Hyflo Super-Cel (g/L)
2.1	5:1	2.50
2.2	7.5:1	3.75
2.3	10:1	5.00

2.4	12.5:1	2.25
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Next test results are shown in Table 9.

Table 9. Trials and steps for the production of gelatin from fish by-products (salmon heads, bones and skins (SHBS)).

TEST	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18
CHEMICAL TREATMENT											
Duration (h)	16	21	21	21	20	20	4	4	3	3	3
Temperature (°C)	Room	Room									
Stirring	Level 4	Level 4	Level 4	Level 5	Level 4	Level 4	Level 4	Level 4	Level 5	Level 4	Level 10
Fish (%)	30	29	20	30	30	20	12	20	40	40	24
NaOH % (w/w)	3	4	4	2	2	3	2	1	2	0,7	0,7
NaOH % (w/v)	0,9	1,2	0,8	0,6	0,6	0,6	0,2	0,2	0,8	0,28	0,17
EXTRACTION											
Time (h)	4	4	4	4	4	4	3	3		3	3
Temperature (°C)	75	75-90	75	75?	75-85	75-85	50	40		60	55
Stirring Level	Level 4	Level 4	Level 4	Level 5	Level 4	Level 4	Level 4	Level 4		Level 10	Level 8
Fish (%)	27	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		40,0	24,0
Exhausted solid (%)	5,7	2,8	4,0	0,0	1,5	0,0	12,0	10,4		37,5	-
PRESS FILTER											
Soil pre-layer (ratio kg/100 L)	1,023	1,023	1,023	-	1,023	1,023	1,364	1,364			
Ratio (kg/m ²)	0,75	0,75	0,75	-	0,75	0,75	1	1			
Soil in product (kg/ 100L)	0,25	0,25	0,25	-	0,25	0,25	0,5	0,5			
Ratio	5:1	5:1	5:1	-	5:1	5:1					
Time (min)	45	90	50	-	60	70		50			
CENTRIFUGE											
Time (min)	120	120	90	-	-	80	40	40			
Volume (L)	500	500	250	-	-	500	500	600			
Stirring (rpm)	12000	12000	12000	-	-	12000	12000	12000			

TEST	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18
Flow rate (L/h)	350	350	150	-	-	350	300	150			
Outlet Pressure (bar)	3	3	3	-	-	3	3	3			
Disc (mm)	59	59	59	-	-	59	59	59			
Inlet °Brix	-	1,5	3	-	-	1	-	1			

2.4.4. Production of enzymes and active peptides from meat by-products

Due to the challenges faced regarding the supply of meat by-products, until M30 it was not possible to carry out any bioprocess related to the production of enzymes and active peptides from meat by-products. Nevertheless, new trials with blood and rabbit skin were done in the next months, following the steps previously described in Section 2.3.3. The performance and results of both bioprocesses are collected in this final deliverable (D3.10) of M48.

For the blood treatment, an alkaline treatment testing some different percentages (w/v) of alkaline chemicals (NaOH was the selected one) at an initial range of temperature of 60°C, following literature, for in between 3 and 6 hours process. All the blood employed in the processes was pig blood (*Sus scrofa domestica*). The chemical hydrolysis parameters are show in Table 10.

Table 10. Chemical blood hydrolysis steps and parameters.

Trial	Filtration	Mechanical lysis (Homogenizer)	% w/v NaOH	pH	Temperature (°C)	Time (h)	rpm
1	Stainless strainer	600 bar	2	12	60	3	60
2	Stainless strainer	600 bar	1	12	60	3	60
3	Stainless strainer	600 bar	2	12	57	6	60
4	Stainless strainer	600 bar	2	12	57	6	60

Regarding the rabbit skin protein extraction, first trials have been developed at lab scale in order to determine the best chemical treatment for this bioprocess. For that, the rabbit skin

was subjected to neutral, acid (1.25 % HCl w/w) and alkaline (1.25 % w/w NaOH) treatments at room temperature overnight.

With the best chemical treatment (alkaline), different concentrations (1.25, 2.5 and 5 % w/w) of the reagent (NaOH) was evaluated at different reaction times (2, 3, 4 and 5h).

Once the appropriate chemical concentration and time were selected, different conditions for enzymatic hydrolysis were studied. Two approaches were tested: enzymatic hydrolysis after the chemical treatment without separating the solid fraction, and enzymatic hydrolysis of the liquid fraction after applying the chemical treatment and a thermal treatment to the solid part. In both cases, the conditions for enzymatic hydrolysis with 0.5 % (w/w protein) of endo-protease at 50°C and pH 8 for 4 h.

2.5. Valorisation of the exhausted solids

After the bioprocesses of the different feedstocks (spent coffee grounds, fish by-products and meat by-products) included in Pilot 1, the exhausted solids are revalorized and sent to Pilot 3 for insect protein production. During this final period, a total amount of 40 kg of exhausted SCG; 100 kg of exhausted fish by-products and 40 kg of meat by-product (rabbit skin) have been sent to Pilot 3.

2.6. Analytical methods

2.6.1. Biomass production

To carry out biomass monitoring during the fermentation process, samples were taken at different times during the process. From each sample, 10 mL (procedure done per triplicate) were separated into previously tared tubes, centrifuged (8000 rpm/10 min) and the supernatant was removed. The resulting biomass was incubated at 105 °C for 48h in order to obtain the dry cell weight (g/L).

2.6.2. Glucose quantification

To quantify the amount of glucose released during enzymatic hydrolysis, a commercial kit is used (Glucose-LQ, Spinreact®). By using this test, glucose oxidase catalyzes the oxidation of glucose to gluconic acid. The formed hydrogen peroxide is detected by a chromogenic oxygen acceptor, phenol,4-aminophenazone in the presence of peroxidase. The intensity of the color formed is proportional to the glucose concentration in the sample.

Glucose analysis is performed measuring the absorbance of the samples at 505 nm. Blank is done with R reagent, while samples are measured by taking 1 mL of R and 10 µL of each sample. To calculate glucose concentration, next equation is needed:

$$\frac{(A)_{Sample} - (A)_{Blank}}{(A)_{Standard} - (A)_{Blank}} \cdot 100 \text{ (Standard conc.)} = \text{mg/dL glucose in the sample}$$

2.6.3. Oils and polyphenols quantification

The oil content was quantified by net weight.

The polyphenol content was analyzed by the Folin-Ciocalteu method. The phenolic compounds react with the Folin-Ciocalteu reagent in a basic medium to give a blue colouring which can be determined spectrophotometrically at 765 nm. This reagent contains a mixture of sodium tungstate and sodium molybdate in phosphoric acid. The yellow phosphomolybdotungstic acid formed, when reduced by the phenolic groups, gives rise to an intense blue complex, the intensity of which is measured to evaluate the polyphenol content.

3. Results of demonstration phase

3.1 Structural composition of the feedstocks

Initial characterizations of the raw materials were conducted by BIOPOLIS. Results for each feedstock are shown below.

Table 11. Structural composition of dried meat by-products

Parameter	Amount (g/100g)
Ash	1.02
Insoluble fiber	1.61
Fats	15.50
Monounsaturated fat	7.66
Polyunsaturated fat	2.11
Saturated fat	5.73
Trans fat	0.13
Carbohydrates	1.19
Moisture	64.00
Protein	14.70
Salt	0.20

Table 12. Structural composition of dried fish by-products

Parameter	Amount (g/100g)
Ash	1.75
Insoluble fiber	1.384
Fats	11.96
Monounsaturated fat	5.22

Parameter	Amount (g/100g)
Polyunsaturated fat	2.94
Saturated fat	3.8
Carbohydrates	<0.1
Moisture	70.5
Protein	15.6
Salt	0.316
Total sugars	<0.1

Table 13. Structural composition of dried spent coffee grounds

Parameter	Amount (g/100g)
Ash	0.6
Insoluble fiber	21.11
Fats	5.25
Monounsaturated fat	0.862
Polyunsaturated fat	1.926
Saturated fat	2.46
Trans fat	0.02
Carbohydrates	6.17
Moisture	64.1
Protein	<0.06
Salt	0.08
Total sugars	1.88

3.2 Production of carotenoids from spent coffee grounds

3.2.1 Sugar release from SCG's enzymatic hydrolysis

Results related to laboratory optimization of enzymatic hydrolysis carried out in BIOPOLIS at laboratory scale are shown in the next tables (from Table 14 to Table 18).

Table 14. Enzymatic SCGs hydrolysis trial for the obtention of glucose.

Trial 1	Enzyme	SCG loading (%) (w/v)	Enzyme concentration (%) (v/v)	Temperature (°C)	pH	Time (h)	Glucose (g/L)
1.1	Celluclast 1.5L	26.21	2	50	4.5	24	4.22
1.2	Viscozyme	26.21	2	50	4.5	24	4.50
1.3	Ultraflo	26.21	2	50	4.5	24	0.94*

In this first trial of enzymatic hydrolysis (Table 14) with conditions of pH 4.5, agitation 200 rpm and the addition of Celluclast 1.5L, Viscozyme and Ultraflo enzymes during 24h gave 4.22, 4.5 and 0.94 grams of glucose per liter, respectively. Ultraflo was submitted to 24 hours more in order to see if glucose concentration would increase. Ultraflo did not release that level of glucose as the other enzymes after 48 hours and due to this, it was discarded.

Table 15. Coffee hydrolysis with 2 enzymes (consecutive addition). Hydrolyzed with an enzyme during 12 hours and 12 hours later with another enzyme at 50°C and pH 4.5

Trial 2	Enzymes and addition order	SCG loading (%) (w/v)	Enzyme 1 (%) v/v	Glucose (g/L)	Enzyme 2 % (w/v)	Glucose (g/L)
2.1	Celluclast 1.5L + Viscozyme	25	2	0.75	2	4.18
2.2	Celluclast + Ultraflo	25	2	0.95	2	0.88
2.3	Viscozyme + Ultraflo	25	2	3.42	2	3.60

In this experimental set of enzymatic hydrolysis (Table 15) at pH 4.5, 50°C for 24 hours, the addition of a second consecutive enzyme is performed. Celluclast 1.5 L + Viscozyme showed 4.18 g/L of glucose and Celluclast + Ultraflo and Viscozyme + Ultraflo showed 0.88 and 3.60 g/L, respectively.

Table 16. Trial based on pH optimization in enzymatic hydrolysis of SCGs using Celluclast enzyme.

Trial 3	Hydrolysis	Time 0	24h	48h	72h
---------	------------	--------	-----	-----	-----

3.1	Celluclast, pH 4.5 / 60°C	0.066 g/L	0.273 g/L	0.292 g/L	0.317 g/L
3.2	Celluclast, pH 5 / 60°C	0.055 g/L	0.252 g/L	0.289 g/L	0.317 g/L
3.3	Celluclast, pH 5.5 / 60°C	0.085 g/L	0.223 g/L	0.271 g/L	0.285 g/L
3.4	Celluclast, pH 6 / 60°C	0.061 g/L	0.297 g/L	0.292 g/L	0.308 g/L

The trial conditions in Table 16 were pH between 4.5 and 6 at 60 °C. The enzymatic dosage was 0.06% and SCG loading was 10% (w/v). At these experiments, maximum concentration of glucose was achieved within trial 3.1.

Table 17. Enzymatic hydrolysis trial with two enzymes added at the beginning of the trial.

Trial 4	Hydrolysis with 2 enzymes	Glucose (g/L)					
		Enzymatic treatment	0	12h	24h	36h	48h
4.1	Celluclast + Clintonzyme	0	0.163	0.177	0.114	0.095	
4.2	Celluclast + Ultraflo	0	0.195	0.085	0.157	0.108	
4.3	Celluclast + Vinotaste	0	0.160	0.160	0.174	0.302	0.214
4.4	Celluclast + Viscozyme	0	0.172	0	0.089	0.060	

Enzymatic hydrolysis trials in Table 17 were carried out using an enzymatic dosage of 0.06% at pH 5 and 60°C (Table 17). The enzymes used were Celluclast with Clintonzyme, Ultraflo, Vinotaste or Viscozyme. Results show that Celluclast + Vinotaste gave the best results at these conditions: 0,214 g/L at 60h.

Table 18. Hydrolysis SCG trial with the addition of two enzymes sequentially.

Trial 5	Viscozyme +Celluclast	Glucose (g/L) T 18h Viscozyme	Glucose (g/L) T 24h Viscozyme + Celluclast	Glucose (g/L) T 48h Viscozyme + Celluclast
5.1	0.5% enzyme	0.473	1.268	1.440
5.2	0.1% enzyme	0.235	0.929	0.376
5.3	0.05% enzyme	0.303	0.597	0.603

The conditions for this trial (Table 18) were 4 % (w/v) of SCG at pH 5.0 and 60°C. First, Viscozyme enzyme was added (0.5%, 0.1% and 0.05%) and agitated at 60°C during 18h. Secondly, the addition of Celluclast was performed at the same concentrations as Viscozyme. Best results of glucose yield (1,440 g/L) were also obtained in the combination of Celluclast and Viscozyme in 48h of reaction and 0,5% of each enzyme.

After the trials carried out at laboratory scale, results from the initial experiments at SAV's pilot plant of enzymatic screening to select the appropriate enzymes and operational parameters for the enzymatic hydrolysis of SCGs are shown in Table 19.

Table 19. Glucose release from SCG's enzymatic hydrolysis.

Enzyme	Enzyme Concentration % (v/v)	SCG loading % (w/v)	pH	Temperature (° C)	Time (h)	Glucose (g/L)
Celluclast 1.5 L	0.0625	10	4,5	50	48	0.26
Celluclast 1.5 L	0.0625	10	5	50	48	0.024
Celluclast 1.5 L	0.0625	10	5	60	48	0.402
Vinotaste Pro	0.0625	10	3	40	48	0.058
Vinotaste Pro	0.0625	10	5	50	48	0.029
Vinotaste Pro	0.0625	10	3	60	48	0.109
Ultraflo	0.0625	10	5	50	48	0.067
Ultraflo	0.0625	10	5	70	48	0.123
Viscozyme	0.0625	10	5	40	48	0.084
Viscozyme	0.0625	10	5	50	48	0.078
Viscozyme	0.0625	10	5	60	48	0.154

As presented in Table 19, the most promising enzymes to carry out the saccharification process from spent coffee grounds are Celluclast 1.5 L, Vinotaste Pro and Viscozyme, as obtained at lab scale, since glucose concentration (g/L) reaches values between 0,1-0,4 in these trials. Because of these first results, next experiments were carried out using these enzymes, although glucose release results were not very high, considering that cellulose concentration in spent coffee grounds is around 7-12 % (Table 2).

Considering the previous results, new experiments (Table 4) were carried out using Celluclast 1.5 L and Vinotaste Pro. These trials were realized under milder conditions (50°C and pH 5), since they present the highest activity at these conditions. Glucose concentration (g/L) obtained in these experiments were 0.110 in H-1, 0.298 in H-2 and 0.368 in H-3.

In order to improve the sugar release from the spent coffee grounds and taking into account that they are lignocellulosic materials, so they have a complex structure that prevents enzymes from binding to the substrate, pretreatment experiments have been designed. The

pretreatment aims to alter the complex polymeric biomass structure by breaking the lignin seal, removing lignin and/or increasing its porosity. The pretreatment meets the following requirements: low energy demand and overall costs, efficient and rapid release of sugars in the subsequent hydrolysis, reducing carbohydrate degradation and avoiding the formation of inhibitory compounds. Alkaline pretreatment disrupts and removes the lignin-carbohydrate structure and causes the biomass to swell, which reduces polymerization and cellulose crystallinity and increases the internal surface area (Valles et al., 2021).

Among the different alkaline reagents, sodium hydroxide leads to a more efficient spent waste delignification. So, NaOH was the reagent used for the next trials for spent coffee hydrolysis in laboratory and pilot scale varying operational conditions. First pretreatment trial was developed with NaOH 0.3M, 10% (w/v) loading SCG at 60°C for 6 hours. After the pretreatment step, pH was adjusted to 5 by using H₂SO₄ 4M and 0,5% (v/v) of Celluclast 1.5 L were added. Enzymatic hydrolysis was developed during 72h at 50°C. After the whole experiment, glucose concentration obtained was 1.33 g/L. Therefore, glucose concentration in the hydrolysate was tripled with respect to the H-3 trial, where the same enzymatic concentration was used, so it has been shown that alkaline pretreatment increases and favors the release of sugars. More experiments were performed in order to optimize the alkaline pretreatment in Biopolis and SAV facilities.

3.2.2 Carotenoids production from SCG

Xanthophyllomyces dendrorhous (formerly *Phaffia rhodozyma*) was selected for the AX production due that *Xanthophyllomyces dendrorhous* is considered by European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) to be suitable for the qualified presumption of safety (QPS) pre-assessment that covers safety concerns for humans, animals and the environment. *X. dendrorhous* is a basidiomycetous yeast that produces AX as a secondary metabolite through the mevalonate pathway

Results from the initial fermentation developed in BIOPOLIS to further optimize the carotenoids production is shown in Table 20.

Table 20. Monitoring results of laboratory fermentation for carotenoid production

Time (h)	OD600nm	Glucose (g/L)	Cell Dry Weight (g/L)
0	1.20	26.00	1.18
19	7.50	24.00	2.80

Time (h)	OD600nm	Glucose (g/L)	Cell Dry Weight (g/L)
28	27.00	10.30	6.54
92	**	0.22	8.75
100	**	0.0	7.01
116	**	0.0	5.15
144	**	0.0	**
166	**	0.0	**

At 98h, since there was no glucose left in the medium, a pulse of 250 mL of coffee hydrolysate was given with a glucose concentration of 4.18 g/L + 5 g/L of yeast extract.

This pulse is the cause of the decrease in dry weight, since a dilution of the medium was produced by adding this volume.

Considering the results obtained, it can be concluded that the fermentation conditions selected are adequate for the yeast growth. In addition, it is observed that the highest consumption of glucose occurs during the period 20-40 h of fermentation, so during this time is when the yeast grows exponentially, reaching a maximum level of biomass production of 8,75 g/L cell dry weight at 92 h.

According to the fermentation trials performed in SAV's pilot plant (Table 20), monitoring results obtained until this moment regarding glucose consumption are displayed in Table 21.

Table 21. SAV pilot plant fermentation tests for carotenoid production.

Time (h)	Glucose concentration (g/L)			
	CAR-1	CAR-2	CAR-3	CAR-4
0	14.00	13.50	20.02	18.60
18	10.82	12.06	18.98	16.90

Glucose concentration (g/L)				
Time (h)	CAR-1	CAR-2	CAR-3	CAR-4
24	5.30	10.79	17.93	15.10
42	2.22	4.50	0.119	0.104
47	0.34	4.16	0.043	0.028
72	*	0.34	0.034	0.011

Regarding biomass production during CAR-1, CAR-2, CAR-3 and CAR-4 fermentations, results are presented in Table 22 and Table 23.

Table 22. Cell wet weight (g/L) results for CAR-1 and CAR-2 fermentation tests.

Cell wet weight (g/L)				
Time (h)	CAR-1	CAR-2	CAR-3	CAR-4
0	32.96	7.92	1.50	10.85
18	14.50	8.48	0.32	13,68
24	14.54	10.20	0.68	*
42	15.40	17.30	3.72	49.57
47	20.14	10.26	4.70	47.84
72	*	15.02	6.00	49.24

Table 23. Cell dry weight (g/L) results for CAR-1 and CAR-2 fermentation tests

Cell dry weight (g/L)				
Time (h)	CAR-1	CAR-2	CAR-3	CAR-4
0	5.04	0.51	0.64	1.08
18	0.94	0.56	0.32	1.70
24	0.94	0.56	0.68	*

Cell dry weight (g/L)				
Time (h)	CAR-1	CAR-2	CAR-3	CAR-4
42	0.98	0.71	3.72	6.78
47	1.48	0.65	4.7	5.84
72	*	0.59	6.0	6.81

Regarding results of monitoring CAR-1 and CAR-2, it can be concluded that exponential growth of *X. dendrorhous* takes place until 40 h of production, since glucose is consumed almost to exhaustion. However, this consumption of glucose does not correspond to the biomass production, since results related to cell dry weight (g/L) do not show an increase in biomass production in any of the trials. However, results of cell wet weight (g/L) show an increase in biomass until 42h. This production of biomass will be next proportional to the carotenoids production.

Nevertheless, during these two bioprocesses of fermentation, the production of the characteristic orange color of carotenoids was not observed, so carotenoids have probably not been produced. This fact agrees with the results of biomass production, since an increase in cell dry weight has hardly been observed throughout the two processes, so it can be concluded that the conditions used in both fermentation processes have not been adequate for the growth of the yeast. That is why in the following processes (CAR-3 and CAR-4) it was decided to supplement the culture medium with yeast extract, since it was assumed that the coffee hydrolysate obtained did not provide certain essential amino acids, vitamins or growth factors necessary for yeast growth.

Results of monitoring CAR-3 and CAR-4 show that yeast extracts enhanced biomass production, since it provides essential amino acids, vitamins or growth factors that were not included in the previous culture medium. These bio-productions also confirm that the exponential growth of yeast takes place during the first 40 h. In CAR-4 the production of biomass reaches the highest yield, so the increase in aeration (from 0.5 to 1 vvm) also benefits yeast growth. In addition, the production of carotenoids in CAR-4 is the highest one obtained: 205.105 mg. This result is translated into 0.26 g carotenoids per kg of SCG.

Despite the results explained above, new tests were carried out. To be specific, nine more tests were done (CAR-5, CAR-6, CAR-7, CAR-8, CAR-9, CAR-10, CAR-11, CAR-12, CAR-13). CAR-10 was discarded due to contamination. Table 24 shows the results obtained from those tests.

Table 24. Cell dry weight (g/L) results from CAR-5 to CAR-13 fermentation tests

Time (h)	CAR-5	CAR-6	CAR-7	CAR-8	CAR-9	CAR-11	CAR-12	CAR-13
0	0,64	0	0	0	0	1,48	0,66	1,44
2	0,5							
15		1,08						
16	0,32							
18				0,97				
19			1,34,					
20		1,7					3,78	
21	0,5				1,42			3,42
22				1,436				
23						6,05		
24	0,68							
25							4,6	
27					2,61			
39		6,78						
40	3,3							
42								
43				3,1	4,72			
44	3,72	6,9						4,78
46						6,26	5,66	
47		5,84		3,48				
48					5,55			
49	4,7							
63		6,81						
64	6							
66				5,18				
67					5,49			5,86
68							6,4	
75					5,375			
86			2,56					

Time (h)	CAR-5	CAR-6	CAR-7	CAR-8	CAR-9	CAR-11	CAR-12	CAR-13
90							7,5	7,58
91					5,55	5,76		
110			3,14					

With the aim of a better understanding, the next figure shows the dry cell biomass variation along the fermentation time. Looking at the figure the illustrated results said that the most productive test was CAR-12 and CAR-1.

Figure 19. Cell Dry biomass variation along the fermentation for CAR-5 to CAR-13

The samples were analyzed and the resulting carotenoid production is shown in the next figure, where it is illustrated that the CAR-12 and CAR-13 have also the highest carotenoid concentration, having CAR-12 the maximum yield.

Figure 20. Y-Astaxanthin concentration in tests CAR-5 to CAR-13

Xanthophyllomyces dendrorhous (formerly *Phaffia rhodozyma*) was selected for the AX production due that *Xanthophyllomyces dendrorhous* is considered by European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) to be suitable for the qualified presumption of safety (QPS) pre-assessment that covers safety concerns for humans, animals and the environment. *X. dendrorhous* is a basidiomycetous yeast that produces AX as a secondary metabolite through the mevalonate pathway. The yield obtained was 0.7 mg of AX/g dry SCG and 0.016 mg AX/g dry cell weight. This yield is smaller than the yield reported with *Sporobolomyces roseus* (Petrik et al., 2014) with a yield of 1.26 mg AX/g of biomass, a fact that suggests that *S. roseus* seems to be a better candidate for the production of carotenoids from SCG. But as commented above, the choice of the *X. dendrorhous* was due that this yeast is considered as qualified presumption of safety by EFSA.

Taking into account the results obtained with *X. dendrorhous*, a test with *Sporobolomyces roseus* was done using the optimized parameters in previous tests with the other yeast. Specifically, it was done with the parameters of CAR-12 due to its good results. The biomass production is shown in the next figure.

Figure 21. Cell Dry biomass variation along the fermentation. for CAR-S1

After the trial with *S. roseus*, the yield of AX produced were <6.06 Y astax mg/SCG kg. Also the total β -carotene concentration was 16.16 mg/kg, these values are positive because it tells that with other growth parameters, *S. roseus* can produce carotenoids at a demi-industrial scale. Figure 22 shows the biomass production of test CAR-S1 compared to the others.

Figure 22. Cell Dry biomass variation along the fermentation for CAR-5 to CAR-13 and CAR-S1

Also, in the next figure the Y astax./SCG mg/kg has been updated with CAR-S1 results.

Figure 23. Y-Astaxanthin concentration in tests CAR-5 to CAR-13 and CAR-S1

3.2.3 Production of gelatin from meat by-products

As previously explained, trials have been developed at lab scale in order to determine the best chemical treatment for this bioprocess. For that, the rabbit skin was subjected to neutral, acid (1.25 % HCl w/w) and alkaline (1.25 % w/w NaOH) treatments at room temperature overnight (Figure 24).

Figure 24. Chemical treatment determination. Neutral, Acid and Basic.

With the best chemical treatment (alkaline), different concentrations (1.25, 2.5 and 5 % w/w) of the reagent (NaOH) was evaluated at different reaction times (2, 3, 4 and 5h), as shown in Table 25.

Table 25. Trials with different NaPOH concentrations (Sample 1: 1,25%, Sample 2: 2.5%; Sample 3: 5%)

Time (h)	Sample 1	Sample 2	Sample 3
	°Brix	°Brix	°Brix
2	5.2	8	14
3	5.8	8.5	14
4	6	8.5	14
5	6	9	14

As can be seen in the monitoring of the three samples from the previous test, at higher doses of NaOH, the gelatin extraction is greater and takes place in a shorter time, so the yield increases with the dose of NaOH. Likewise, at higher doses, greater hydration of the solid samples is observed, since their weight increases with respect to the liquid weight. At very high doses, such as 5% NaOH, the entire solid is degraded in the broth, so the gelatin extraction is complete.

Once the appropriate chemical concentration and time were selected, different conditions for enzymatic hydrolysis were studied. Two approaches were tested: enzymatic hydrolysis after the chemical treatment without separating the solid fraction, and enzymatic hydrolysis of the liquid fraction after applying the chemical treatment and a thermal treatment to the solid part. In both cases, the conditions for enzymatic hydrolysis with 0.5 % (w/w protein) of endo-protease at 50°C and pH 8 for 4 h. First approach is shown in Table 26 and Table 27 and in Figure 25 the feedstock treated is also shown.

Table 26. Neutral and alkaline maceration results.

Neutral and alkaline maceration results				
Sample	Time (h)	final pH	stabilized pH	° Brix
A.1	1	12,44	8,43	4
A.2	1	12,40	8,38	4,5
B.1	1	6,04	8,15	1
B.2	1	5,74	8,07	1

Table 27. Enzymatic hydrolysis results.

Enzymatic hydrolysis					
Sample	Time (h)	final pH	° Brix	Solid weigh (g)	Liquid weigh (g)
A.1	4	7,92	6,5	22,05	1052,67
A.2	4	7,89	6,5	27,36	1125,63
B.1	4	7,50	5	33,79	796,43
B.2	4	7,49	5	50,68	794,66

Figure 25. A and B samples after maceration and Enzymatic hydrolysis.

As can be seen in Figure 25, in samples A (A.1 and A.2) 3 phases have formed: in the first layer an emulsion of lipids and proteins is observed, a second layer of collagen hydrolyzate and third layer of solids. It is thought that the emulsion layer has formed due to the large free amount of protein in the medium (a result of alkaline maceration) and the low concentration of added enzyme. Thus, the low enzyme concentration and the high protein concentration caused saturation of the enzyme and low hydrolysis.

In both samples and as can be seen in Figure 26, the solid exhausted from both processes corresponds to the fraction of hair that the samples contained, the skin having completely degraded.

Figure 26. Exhausted solids A and B.

Furthermore, four more trials were made and the results are shown in Table 28.

Table 28. Alkaline and Neutral maceration results in C and D samples.

Maceration results					
Sample	Time (h)	Final pH	° Brix	Solid weigh (g)	Liquid weigh (g)
C.1	1	12,52	4,5	315,31	469,32
C.2	1	12,64	4,8	314,27	459,26
D.1	1	6,23	0,5	101,37	699,21
D.2	1	6,23	0,5	104,79	690,48

Figure 27. Solids C and D after alkaline and neutral maceration process, respectively.

The solids resulting from processes C and D of alkaline and neutral maceration, respectively, show remarkable differences. As mentioned previously, the alkaline maceration process favors the opening of the collagen molecule and therefore its hydration, causing a considerable

increase in the weight of the skin (up to 6 times its initial weight). This hydration process can be analyzed at a glance, as the skin increases its volume and acquires a more elastic texture, conditioning itself for subsequent processes. On the other hand, neutral maceration hydrates the dry material, but does not favor the hydration of collagen, so the residue only doubles its initial weight and the same elasticity is not observed.

After maceration, the solid material was stored in a freezer to continue with thermal extraction later. The results of the extraction process are shown in Table 29 and Figure 28 Figure 29 Figure 30.

Table 29. Thermal extraction results.

Thermal extraction										
Sample	Time (h)	pH ₀	pH _F	P ₀ solid (g)	P _F solid (g)	P ₀ liquid (g)	P _F liquid (g)	° Brix	Total gelatin (g)	Extraction yield (% g gelatin/g skin)
C.1	3	4,54	4,12	170,03	143,87	629,97	686,65	1,5	10,8	21,6
C.2	3	4,76	6,61	264,79	131,75	535,21	682,20	1,3	9,36	18,72
D.1	3	4,93	5,52	95,11	93,76	704,89	701,71	0,1	0,72	1,44
D.2	3	4,75	5,52	98,29	93,91	701,71	700,04	0,3	2,16	4,32

Figure 28. Result of thermal extraction.

Figure 29. Exhausted solid from tests C and D after maceration and thermal extraction.

Figure 30. Liquid resulting from the gelatin extraction process.

As observed in the extraction results of tests C and D, the performance of the process is higher for both tests C, since the °Brix measured are higher in both cases with respect to the results of D. Taking into account that the maximum °Brix extraction that can be achieved are 3.75, since it has been estimated that each solid sample contains 30g of proteins (6.25 °Brix if 50g of dry skin are considered), the maximum experimental yields obtained for samples C.1 and C.2 have been 21.6 and 18.72%, respectively.

In this case, the conditioning of the solid with the alkaline treatment favors the extraction of gelatin, since it allows better hydration of the solid and encourages the collagen chains to begin to separate, facilitating and improving, as has been observed, the process of extraction.

After the enzymatic hydrolysis process, the formation of granules is again observed in tests D.1 and D.2 (Table 30), probably resulting from the emulsion of lipids and proteins, although, in this case, the emulsion is less than that observed in A.1 and A.2 (Table 26).

Table 30. Enzymatic hydrolysis results

Enzymatic hydrolysis					
Sample	Time (h)	pH ₀	° Brix	P ₀ liquid(g)	P _F solid (g)
C.1	4	8,55	1,8	686,65	683,50
C.2	4	8,20	1,5	682,20	680,29
D.1	4	8,26	0,4	701,71	629,33
D.2	4	8,23	0,5	700,04	686,64

3.2.4 Production of gelatin from fish by-products

For the extraction of gelatine, batches of 500 kg of fish-by products were used through the process described in section 2.3.2. Operational parameters during chemical and thermal treatment are essential for the extraction process. During chemical treatment using NaOH concentrations between 2-4 % (w/w) denaturation of collagen occurs, so the intermolecular bonds stabilizing the quaternary structure of collagen are broken. The raw material is then subjected to a hot-water extraction at 75°C, during which collagen is thermally denatured, thus the bonds stabilizing the tertiary structure are broken. The result is the preparation of a gelatin solution of polypeptide chains.

In order to increase the gelatin production, variation of NaOH concentration and loading of raw material has been modified in each process. According to the trials, results of gelatin production are shown in Table 31. The best conditions for gelatin production obtained until now are those that correspond to P-18.

Table 31. Gelatin production from fish by-products

Trial	Yield (g gelatin/kg fish)
P-0	21.50
P-1	-
P-2	-
P-3	6.40
P-4	55.80
P-5	83.00
P-6	41.23
P-7	90.23
P-17	112.5
P-18	131.25
P-19	61.22

Gelatine yield also depends on the type of feedstock treated. From P-0 to P-2 raw material was composed of muscle meat and viscera of multiple big fishes, since the rest of feedstock received from MercaValencia was in too big parts to be crushed and treated in SAV's pilot plant. It can be seen in the results obtained that these fish by-products do not contain enough gelatin, thus collagen is mainly present in skin and bones. Considering this, other fish by-products mainly composed of salmon bones, skin and heads started to be treated from P-4 onwards. Results obtained show that bones, skin and head contain a high amount of gelatin, so this type of waste is more suitable for the extraction of collagen. Gelatin extracted in trials from P-8 to P-10 was lost during centrifugation, and from P-11 to P-16, the results were discarded due to temperature increment in an anomaly way and in P-16 because of equipment obstruction.

For the production of active peptides (hydrolyzed collagen), AMD-BIOPOLIS tested 3 different proteases (ASP, Neutrase and Alcalase) to assess the oxidative power of the peptides obtained from the hydrolysis. The FRAP assay was used to assess the oxidative power of the peptides. This assay measures the reduction of ferric ion (Fe^{3+})-ligand complex to the intensely blue-colored ferrous (Fe^{2+}) complex by antioxidants in an acidic medium. The dosage and conditions of the FRAP essays are shown in Table 32.

Table 32. Dosage and conditions of the FRAP essays

Dried gelatine (g)	H2O	pH	Enzyme	Temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	Time (h)
2g	50ml	2.0	ASP 2% (w:v) (1g)	37	4
2g	50ml	7.0	Neutrase 2% (w:v) (1g)	50	4
2g	50ml	8.0	Alcalase 2% (w:v) (1g)	50	4

Table 33. Fe^{2+} concentration (μM) of the FRAP essays for different proteases

Treatment	Gelatine Fe^{2+} (μM)	Hydrolyzed Gelatine Fe^{2+} (μM)	ΔFe^{2+} (μM)
Gelatine + Alcalase	30,978	43,715	12,737
Gelatine + Neutrase	30,978	43,132	12,154
Gelatine + ASP	30,978	34,19	3,212

From the tests shown in Table 33, it was determined that Alcalase produces active peptides with bigger oxidative power. For this reason, Alcalase was used for the hydrolysis of gelatine. The steps followed for the production of hydrolyzed collagen are shown in the following Table 34. Figure 31 shows a sample of the gelatine and hydrolyzed collagen obtained.

Table 34. Trials and steps for the production of hydrolyzed collagen from fish by-products (salmon skins).

HYDROLYZED COLLAGEN	
CHEMICAL TREATMENT	
Duration (h)	2
Temperature (°C)	Room
Stirring	Level 8
Fish (%)	54
NaOH %(w/w)	0,7
NaOH % (w/v)	0,17
EXTRACTION	
Time (h)	3
Temperature (°C)	55
Stirring Level	Level 8
Fish (%)	54,4
Exhausted solid (%)	-
PRESS FILTER	
	Day 2
Soil pre-layer (ratio kg/100 L)	0,68
Ratio (kg/m ²)	0,5
Soil in product (kg/ 100L)	0,45
Ratio	
Time (h)	6
CENTRIFUGE	
Time (min)	90
Volume (L)	500
Stirring (rpm)	12000
Flow rate (L/h)	350
Outlet Pressure (bar)	3
Disc (mm)	59
Inlet °Brix	3,5

HYDROLYZED COLLAGEN	
UF	
Time inside (h)	2
Inlet volume (L)	450
Outlet °Brix	3,8
Final weigh (kg)	64
Outlet °Brix	14
ENZYMATIC HYDROLYSIS	
Time (h)	2
Volume (L)	64 (70 final)
Inlet °Brix	10
Initial temperature (°C)	60
initial pH	9
Enzyme (% (p/p protein)	0,5
FLASH EVAPORATOR	
Duration (h)	2
Temperature (°C)	140
Pressure (bar)	4
Inlet Volume (L)	70
°Brix inlet	11
Outlet Volume (L)	12,4
°Brix outlet	44
ROTARY EVAPORATOR	
Initial weight	12,4
°Inlet Brix	44
final weigh (kg)	9,26
Outlet °Brix	57
Temperature (°C)	60
Vacuum pressure (bar)	0,93

Figure 31. Gelatine (left) and hydrolyzed collagen (right) produced from fish by-products.

3.2.5 Production of organic fertilizer from meat by-products

All SAV trials for the production of organic fertilizer from Mercavalencia slaughterhouse blood did obtain satisfactory results. When employing hydrolysed blood as a blending raw material for the production of organic fertilizers, one of the aspects more interesting to look at in the analytics is nitrogen (N), but also phosphorus (P) and iron (Fe). All samples, for being qualified as "optimum" for being used in fertilizer should surpass the 2% of Nitrogen content, which they did. The range fluctuated between 2% and 2,5%.

Also after the trials we observed that in the first place, at less than 1% concentration of alkaline the blood does not hydrolyze enough, and ends up coagulating. This a logistical problem for its future transport and employment (liquid phase is better, and once coagulated, working with "jelly" type products becomes harsh). Also, at smoothly lower temperatures, the chemical reaction still occurred perfectly, helping in higher TRLs to mitigate our economical and environmental impact. Lastly, the minimum time needed is 3 hours. Also, the more time is left of the chemical hydrolysis running, you will reach the highest N %, but over the 5-6 hours, it stops increasing. 3 hours then showed the most optimal time.

On the Table 35 can be shown one of the analytics for a standard sample, with all its fertilizer interesting parameters. The other analytics arose with very similar results.

Table 35. Hydrolysate blood parameters.

Hydrolysed blood parameters		
Parameter	Result	Unit
Conductivity	6600	$\mu\text{S/cm}$ 25 oC
P total	1.1	% P ₂ O ₅
Ca	383	mg/kg
Mg	124.5	mg/kg
Na	>2	%
Fe	2092.3	mg/kg
Mn	<2	mg/kg
Cu	7.7	mg/kg
Zn	14.2	mg/kg
Ratio C/N	3.5	
Total organic C s/s	46.2	% s/s
Total N s/s	13.2	% s/s
Total N	2.3	%
Organic matter	14.4	%
Humidity	82.6	%
Total organic C	8	%
K	6039	mg/kg

3.2.6 Extraction of oil and polyphenols

For the extraction of oil and polyphenols, the SCGs were dried at 105°C during 24 hours to remove the moisture. During this process, the mass of the feedstock was reduced up to 60%.

Then, the dried SCGs were introduced in the soxhlet shown in Figure 32. Batches of 3Kg were introduced in the top side of the soxhlet. This soxhlet has a balloon with a capacity of 50 liters.

In the case of oil extraction, hexane was used as the solvent for the solid-liquid extraction. 40 liters of hexane were introduced in the soxhlet. The ratio substrate/solvent was defined by AMD-Wild at the laboratory scale. The extraction of coffee oil was carried out at 80°C in vacuum conditions during 9 hours. Figure 32 shows the soxhlet during the coffee oil extraction with hexane. After this process, the solvent was transferred progressively by vacuum suction to the rotavapor for the liquid/liquid separation, see Figure 33. In this process, 80°C and vacuum conditions were used to recover the hexane. The yield of the process was 14% w/w of coffee oil from the dried SCGs. Table 36 shows the fatty acid characterization of a sample of dried SCG. As shown in the table, the total fat corresponds to 14.62% w/w. This means the process extraction with hexane was able to extract 95% of the total fats in the SCGs.

Table 36. Fatty acid distribution for SCG

Parameter	Amount (g/100g)
Monounsaturated fat	1.74
Polyunsaturated fat	5.77
Saturated fat	7.1
Trans fat	14
Total fat	14.62

Figure 32. Soxhlet during the SCG oil extraction with hexane.

Figure 33. Rotavapor of 20 liters capacity during the coffee oil/hexane separation.

Figure 34. Sample of coffee oil extracted from the SCGs.

For the polyphenol extraction, batches of 3Kg of dry SCG were introduced in the Soxhlet. In this case, the Solid-Liquid extraction was carried out with water as a solvent, see Figure 35 at SAV. The Soxhlet operated at 60°C in vacuum conditions. After this stage, the results obtained are shown in Figure 36 and Figure 37.

Figure 35. Soxhlet during polyphenol extraction from SCG.

Figure 36. GAE concentration (mg/L) obtained after solid-liquid extraction.

Figure 37. mg of Gallic Acid per g of SCG obtained after solid-liquid extraction.

After the Solid-Liquid extraction a Liquid-Liquid extraction was done using the rotary evaporator to separate the solvent from the extracted polyphenols. The results are shown in Figure 38 Figure 39.

Figure 38. GAE concentration (mg/L) obtained after liquid-liquid extraction.

Figure 39. mg of Gallic Acid per g of SCG obtained after liquid-liquid extraction.

Taking into account all the values presented above, the actual extract volume concentration (%) is shown in Table 37.

Table 37. Actual extract volume concentration

Test	Actual concentration (%)
S1 RV-1	98,3
S1 RV-2	93,8
S1 RV-3	95,6
S2 RV-1	87,5
S4 RV-1	92,5
S6 RV-1	97,8
S6 - RV2 + RV3	98,1
S7 RV-1	95,0
S8 RV-1	89,1

The polyphenol determination was performed carrying out the Folin-Ciocalteu method. It is based on the fact that phenolic compounds react with the Folin-Ciocalteu reagent, at basic pH, giving rise to a blue color that can be determined spectrophotometrically at 765 nm. This reagent contains a mixture of sodium tungstate and sodium molybdate in phosphoric acid and reacts with the phenolic compounds present in the sample.

To calculate the total polyphenol content (TPC) this assay is used. To carry out this method, solutions of sodium carbonate (7.5 g/L) and Folin-Ciocalteu solution (10% v/v) are first prepared.

The procedure to follow is the following:

- To make the standard curve, 30 mL of the Folin-Ciocalteu solution (10% v/v) and 30 mL of the sodium carbonate solution (7.5 g/L) will be prepared.
- To 100 μ L of the standard/extract solutions, 0.75 mL of the Folin-Ciocalteu solution (10% v/v) is added. The mixture is kept for 5 min at room temperature and in the dark.
- Next, 0.75 mL of the sodium carbonate solution (7.5 g/L) is added. The mixture is kept for 1 h in the dark with intermittent shaking.
- Finally, the absorbance of the samples at 765 nm is measured by using the spectrophotometer.

After creating the standard curve, the absorbance results of the samples are interpolated and the equivalent gallic acid concentration (mg GAE/L) is calculated.

The total content of phenolic compounds is expressed as mg gallic acid equivalent per dry weight material (mg GAE/100 g SCG).

$$\frac{\text{mg GAE}}{100\text{g sample}} = \frac{\text{mg GAE result}}{L} \times \frac{\text{solvent (volume)}}{\text{substrate extraction (g)}} \times 100$$

4. Economic Analysis

For the economic analysis, the most relevant economic data of the processes were considered in a cost-benefit analysis. First, a brief market analysis about the average price of every product was done; the prices are shown in Table 38:

Table 38. Average price for products tested in Pilot 1

Product	Units	Quantity	Price (€)	Reference
Hydrolyzed Collagen	kg	1	41	
Gelatine	kg	1	35	
Coffee oil	L	1	10	
Carotenoids	kg	1	300	
Blood biofertilizer	L	1	5	
Polyphenols	g	1	35	

To develop a realistic economic analysis about the feasibility of the study, the yields reported in this deliverable were used in this section.

The gelatin production is going to be the first process to be analyzed. As shown in Table 38, it has an average price of 35€/kg. For the economic analysis three scenarios were established with three different market prices, and all the calculations were done with 1 tonne as the final amount of the product: 42000€/t as a higher price scenario, 35000€/t, and 28000€/t as the lower market price scenario.

For direct costs during the process, all the energy consumption was included. The mechanical pre-treatment, the chemical pre-treatment, the extraction, the filtration, centrifugation, ultrafiltration, and the drying process was analyzed, with all the utilities involved within the process. The study was made to prove the scalability in an economical way, from year 1 to year 10 considering also the equipment depreciation.

Furthermore, every feedstock and reagents were considered also projecting three different scenarios where the main feedstock (fish and meat by-products) changes its prices. The first scenario is for the one 0.8€/kg of feedstock, the second for 1€/kg and the third is where the feedstock reaches the higher price, 2€/kg. Also, the cleaning reagents and water were included. Moreover, for the variable cost analysis, feedstock transport, operator on the plant, maintenance, and facility rent was included in this kind.

As shown in Table 39 and Figure 40, the production and commercialization of gelatine can be profitable from the second year with profit margins around 70-80%.

Table 39. Gross profit percentage estimation in gelatin production for 3 scenarios and sale prices.

Scenario/Year	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4	Year 5	Year 6	Year 7	Year 8	Year 9	Year 10
Sale price 28000€/t. Scenario 1	-93%	32%	55%	62%	68%	69%	76%	76%	77%	77%
Sale price 28000€/t. Scenario 2	-97%	31%	54%	61%	68%	68%	76%	76%	76%	77%
Sale price 28000€/t. Scenario 3	-	24%	50%	58%	65%	66%	73%	74%	74%	74%
Sale price 35000€/t. Scenario 1	-63%	45%	63%	69%	74%	75%	81%	81%	81%	82%
Sale price 35000€/t. Scenario 2	-67%	43%	63%	69%	74%	74%	80%	81%	81%	81%
Sale price 35000€/t. Scenario 3	-85%	38%	59%	66%	72%	73%	78%	79%	79%	79%
Sale price 42000€/t. Scenario 1	-42%	53%	69%	74%	79%	79%	84%	84%	84%	85%
Sale price 42000€/t. Scenario 2	-45%	52%	69%	74%	78%	79%	83%	84%	84%	84%
Sale price 42000€/t. Scenario 3	-61%	48%	66%	72%	77%	77%	82%	82%	82%	83%

Figure 40. MVB growth from year 1 to year 10 of gelatin production.

The next analysis is about hydrolyzed collagen production. As shown in Table 38, the hydrolyzed collagen has an average price of 41€/kg. For the economic analysis three scenarios were established with three different market prices. All the calculations were done with 1 tonne as the final amount of the product: 48000€/t as a higher price scenario, 41000€/t, and 34000€/t as the lower market price scenario.

For direct costs during the process all the energy consumption was included. The mechanical pre-treatment, the chemical pre-treatment, the extraction, the filtration, centrifugation,

ultrafiltration, nanofiltration, and the drying process was analyzed, with all the utilities involved within the process. The study was made to prove the scalability in an economical way, from year 1 to year 10 considering, also, the equipment depreciation.

Furthermore, every feedstock and reagents were considered also projecting three different scenarios where the main feedstock (fish and meat by-products) changes its prices. The first scenario is for the one 0.8€/kg of feedstock, the second for 1€/kg and the third is where the feedstock reaches the higher price, 2€/kg. Also, the cleaning reagents and water were included. Moreover, for the variable cost analysis, feedstock transport, operator on the plant, maintenance, and facility rent was included in this kind.

As shown in Table 40 and Figure 41, the production and commercialization of hydrolyzed collagen can be profitable from the second year similar as in the gelatine process with profit margins around 60-80%.

Table 40. Gross profit percentage estimation in hydrolyzed collagen production for 3 scenarios and sale prices

Scenario/Year	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4	Year 5	Year 6	Year 7	Year 8	Year 9	Year 10
Sale price 28000€/t. Scenario 1	-93%	32%	55%	62%	68%	69%	76%	76%	77%	77%
Sale price 28000€/t. Scenario 2	-97%	31%	54%	61%	68%	68%	76%	76%	76%	77%
Sale price 28000€/t. Scenario 3	-118%	24%	50%	58%	65%	66%	73%	74%	74%	74%
Sale price 35000€/t. Scenario 1	-63%	45%	63%	69%	74%	75%	81%	81%	81%	82%
Sale price 35000€/t. Scenario 2	-67%	43%	63%	69%	74%	74%	80%	81%	81%	81%
Sale price 35000€/t. Scenario 3	-85%	38%	59%	66%	72%	73%	78%	79%	79%	79%
Sale price 42000€/t. Scenario 1	-42%	53%	69%	74%	79%	79%	84%	84%	84%	85%
Sale price 42000€/t. Scenario 2	-45%	52%	69%	74%	78%	79%	83%	84%	84%	84%
Sale price 42000€/t. Scenario 3	-61%	48%	66%	72%	77%	77%	82%	82%	82%	83%

Figure 41. MVB growth from year 1 to year 10 of hydrolyzed collagen production

The hydrolyzed blood is the next product to be analyzed. As shown in Table 38, it has an average price of 5€/L. For the economic analysis three scenarios were established with three different market prices. All the calculations were done with 1m³ as the final amount of the product: 1000€/m³ as a higher price scenario, 700€/m³, and 500€/m³ as the lower market price scenario.

For direct costs during the process all the energy consumption was included. The thermal pre-treatment, the mechanical pre-treatment, the chemical hydrolysis, and the product maintenance was analyzed, with all the utilities involved within the process. The study was made to prove the scalability in an economical way, from year 1 to year 10 considering, also, the equipment depreciation.

Furthermore, every feedstock and reagents were considered also projecting three different scenarios where the main feedstock (blood) changes its prices. The first scenario is for the one 40€/m³ of blood, the second for 55€/m³ of blood and the third is where the feedstock reaches the higher price, 70€/m³ of blood. Also, the cleaning reagents and water were included. Moreover, for the variable cost analysis, feedstock transport, operator on the plant, maintenance, and rent was included in this kind.

The scalability and feasibility for 10 years is shown in Table 39. It shows that in the first scenario where the sale price is low, the first year there is a 14% maximum loss, but right in the second year, there is a 5% minimum gain, and it keeps increasing with the passing years. Figure 1 shows the growth through the years. It illustrates the fact that the sales price affects way more than the scenario type.

As shown in Table 40 and Figure 41, the production and commercialization of hydrolyzed blood can be profitable from the second year, with profit margins between 30-50%.

Table 40. Gross profit percentage estimation in hydrolyzed blood production for 3 scenarios and sale prices

Price/Year	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4	Year 5	Year 6	Year 7	Year 8	Year 9	Year 10
Sale price: 500€/m ³ . Scenario 1	-19%	5%	13%	14%	17%	17%	17%	17%	18%	18%
Sale price: 500€/m ³ . Scenario 2	-23%	1%	10%	12%	14%	14%	15%	15%	15%	15%
Sale price: 500€/m ³ . Scenario 3	-26%	-2%	7%	9%	11%	12%	12%	12%	12%	12%
Sale price: 700€/m ³ . Scenario 1	11%	30%	36%	37%	39%	39%	40%	40%	40%	40%
Sale price: 700€/m ³ . Scenario 2	8%	27%	34%	35%	37%	38%	38%	38%	38%	38%
Sale price: 700€/m ³ . Scenario 3	6%	25%	32%	33%	35%	36%	36%	36%	36%	36%
Sale price: 1000€/m ³ . Scenario 1	35%	50%	54%	55%	57%	57%	57%	57%	57%	57%
Sale price: 1000€/m ³ . Scenario 2	34%	48%	53%	54%	55%	56%	56%	56%	56%	56%
Sale price: 1000€/m ³ . Scenario 3	32%	46%	52%	52%	54%	54%	54%	54%	54%	54%

Figure 41. MVB growth from year 1 to year 10 of bio-fertilizer from blood.

The oils from SCG are going to be the next product to be analyzed. As shown in Table 38, it has an average price of 10€/l. For the economic analysis three scenarios were established with three

different market prices: 20€/l as a higher price scenario, 10€/l, and 5€/l as the lower market price scenario.

For direct costs during the process all the energy consumption was included. The coffee drying, the solid-liquid extraction and the liquid-liquid extraction was analyzed, with all the utilities involved within the process. The study was made to prove the scalability in an economical way, from year 1 to year 10 considering, also, the equipment depreciation.

Furthermore, every feedstock and reagents were considered also projecting three different scenarios where the main feedstock (SCG) changes its prices. The first scenario is for the one 0.10€/kg of SCG, the second for 0.30€/kg of SCG and the third is where the feedstock reaches the higher price, 0.50€/kg of SCG. Also, the cleaning reagents and water were included. Moreover, for the variable cost analysis, feedstock transport, operator on the plant, maintenance, and rent was included in this kind.

The scalability and feasibility for 10 years are shown in Table 40. It shows that in every scenario the process is not profitable. Figure 41 shows the decreasing of the profitability through the years. It illustrates the fact that the sales price affects way more than the scenario type. The process extracted almost 100% of the total available fat in the feedstock but the scalability of the process is not profitable due that the Soxhlet used in the pilot can not fit more SCG and due that there is a 7% of solvent loss in the extraction. This suggests that a better design of the Soxhlet with a greater capacity for the feedstock input would obtain a better scalability. Also, after the experience of pilot 2, the extraction of coffee oil is more favorable with Supercritical CO₂.

Table 41. Gross profit percentage estimation in coffee oil extraction for 3 scenarios and sale prices.

Price/year	Year1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4	Year 5	Year 6	Year 7	Year 8	Year 9	Year 10
Sale price 5€/L. Scenario 1	-176%	-269%	-374%	-478%	-580%	-578%	-575%	-573%	-571%	-569%
Sale price 5€/L. Scenario 2	-176%	-269%	-374%	-478%	-580%	-578%	-576%	-573%	-571%	-569%
Sale price 5€/L. Scenario 3	-176%	-269%	-374%	-478%	-580%	-578%	-576%	-574%	-571%	-569%
Sale price 10€/L. Scenario 1	-174%	-263%	-363%	-460%	-554%	-552%	-550%	-548%	-546%	-544%
Sale price 10€/L. Scenario 2	-174%	-263%	-363%	-460%	-554%	-552%	-550%	-548%	-546%	-544%
Sale price 10€/L. Scenario 3	-174%	-263%	-363%	-460%	-555%	-552%	-550%	-548%	-546%	-544%
Sale price 20€/L. Scenario 1	-170%	-252%	-343%	-428%	-509%	-507%	-505%	-503%	-501%	-499%
Sale price 20€/L. Scenario 2	-170%	-252%	-343%	-428%	-509%	-507%	-505%	-503%	-501%	-499%
Sale price 20€/L. Scenario 3	-170%	-252%	-343%	-428%	-509%	-507%	-505%	-503%	-501%	-499%

Figure 42. MVB growth from year 1 to year 10 of oils extraction.

The next analysis is about the carotenoid production. As shown in Table 38, carotenoids have an average price of 5500€/kg. For the economic analysis three scenarios were established with three different market prices. All the calculations were done with 1kg as the final amount of the product: 7500€/kg as a higher price scenario, 5500€/kg, and 3500€/kg as the lower market price scenario.

For direct costs during the process all the energy consumption was included. The coffee drying, the chemical pre-treatment, the enzymatic hydrolysis, the fermentation process, and the cell lysis and carotenoid concentration and homogenization was analyzed, with all the utilities involved within the process. The study was made to prove the scalability in an economical way, from year 1 to year 10 considering, also, the equipment depreciation.

Furthermore, every feedstock and reagents were considered also projecting three different scenarios where the main feedstock (SCG) changes its prices. The first scenario is for the one 0.10€/kg of SCG, the second for 0.30€/kg of SCG and the third is where the feedstock reaches the higher price, 0.50€/kg of SCG. Also, the cleaning reagents and water were included. Moreover, for the variable cost analysis, feedstock transport, operator on the plant, maintenance, and facility rent was included in this kind.

The scalability and profitability for 10 years are shown in Table 42. It shows that in every scenario there is only loss in the process. The analysis shows that the yields of carotenoid produced, and the batch quantity are too low to reach gains in the market. However, as shown in Figure 43, after the fifth year, the losses start to decrease. This means that with a higher carotenoid production yield, the process could be profitable, but with the current obtained data only the scalability has been proved.

Table 42. Gross profit percentage estimation in carotenoid extraction for 3 scenarios and sale prices

Price/Year	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4	Year 5	Year 6	Year 7	Year 8	Year 9	Year 10
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Sale price 3500€/kg. Scenario 1	-134%	150%	-174%	-206%	-248%	-246%	-239%	-237%	-234%	-232%
Sale price 3500€/kg. Scenario 2	-134%	-151%	-175%	-207%	-250%	-247%	-241%	-238%	-236%	-233%
Sale price 3500€/kg. Scenario 3	-135%	-151%	-175%	-208%	-251%	-248%	-242%	-240%	-237%	-234%
Sale price 5500€/kg. Scenario 1	-124%	-135%	-151%	-172%	-197%	-195%	-190%	-188%	-185%	-183%
Sale price 5500€/kg. Scenario 2	-124%	-136%	-152%	-173%	-199%	-196%	-191%	-189%	-187%	-184%
Sale price 5500€/kg. Scenario 3	-125%	-136%	-152%	-174%	-200%	-198%	-192%	-190%	-188%	-186%
Sale price 7500€/kg. Scenario 1	-115%	-122%	-132%	-144%	-160%	-158%	-153%	-151%	-149%	-147%
Sale price 7500€/kg. Scenario 2	-115%	-122%	-132%	-145%	-161%	-159%	-154%	-152%	-150%	-148%
Sale price 7500€/kg. Scenario 3	-116%	-123%	-133%	-146%	-162%	-160%	-155%	-153%	-151%	-149%

Figure 43. MVB growth from year 1 to year 10 of carotenoid production.

Finally, the polyphenols from SCG are going to be the last product to be analyzed. As shown in Table 38, polyphenols have an average price of 30€/g. For the economic analysis three scenarios were established with three different market prices. All the calculations were done with 1g as the final amount of the product: 50€/g as a higher price scenario, 35€/g, and 24,5€/g as the lower market price scenario.

For direct costs during the process all the energy consumption was included. The coffee drying, the solid-liquid extraction and the liquid-liquid extraction was analyzed, with all the utilities involved within the process. The study was made to prove the scalability in an economical way, from year 1 to year 10 considering, also, the equipment depreciation.

Furthermore, every feedstock and reagents were considered also projecting three different scenarios where the main feedstock (SCG) changes its prices. The first scenario is for the one 0.10€/kg of SCG, the second for 0.30€/kg of SCG and the third is where the feedstock reaches the higher price, 0.50€/kg of SCG. Also, the cleaning reagents and water were included. Moreover, for the variable cost analysis, feedstock transport, operator on the plant, maintenance, and rent was included in this kind.

As shown in Table 43 and Figure 44, the extraction and commercialization of polyphenols can be profitable from the first year as the process with water extraction is relatively simple and there are not expensive costs due to solvent loss as in the case of coffee oil extraction.

Table 43. Gross profit percentage estimation in polyphenols extraction for 3 scenarios and sale prices

	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4	Year 5	Year 6	Year 7	Year 8	Year 9	Year 10
Sale price 24.5€/g Scenario 1	30%	25%	30%	32%	34%	34%	59%	59%	59%	59%
Sale price 24.5€/g Scenario 2	30%	25%	29%	32%	34%	34%	59%	59%	59%	59%
Sale price 24.5€/g Scenario 3	30%	25%	29%	32%	33%	34%	59%	59%	59%	59%
Sale price 35€/g Scenario 1	46%	45%	49%	51%	52%	53%	71%	71%	71%	71%
Sale price 35€/g Scenario 2	46%	44%	49%	51%	52%	52%	70%	71%	71%	71%
Sale price 35€/g Scenario 3	46%	44%	49%	51%	52%	52%	70%	71%	71%	71%
Sale price 50€/g Scenario 1	60%	60%	63%	65%	66%	66%	79%	79%	79%	79%
Sale price 50€/g Scenario 2	60%	60%	63%	65%	66%	66%	79%	79%	79%	79%
Sale price 50€/g Scenario 3	59%	59%	63%	65%	66%	66%	79%	79%	79%	79%

Figure 44. MVB growth from year 1 to year 10 of polyphenols extraction

5. Conclusions

Pilot 1 demonstrated the establishment of new value chains for urban biowaste (i.e. SCGs and fish and meat by-products) utilization for the production of higher value purpose products (i.e. gelatine, hydrolyzed collagen, carotenoids, coffee oil and polyphenols) in a city context.

Spent coffee grounds were recovered from the HoReCa sector (Hotels, Restaurants and Cafes) through different restaurants located in Valencia (Spain) while fish and meat by-products were collected from local markets (MercaValencia) and retail companies.

For collagen and hydrolysed collagen production from fish by-products, several trials of raw materials were tested until the raw material was better selected into fish skin. Afterwards, the process was escalated with batches of 500 kg of fish skin. The parameters such as raw material loading (10-30 w/v), NaOH concentration (2-4 w/w), temperature of thermal hydrolysis and time of reaction were optimized in order to achieve the maximum yield of gelatin production. The maximum yield obtained was 131.25 g gelatin per kg of fish by-product at 24% (w/w) loading, 0.7% (w/w) NaOH in chemical treatment and thermal treatment at 60°C and 3 hours. The yields were very close to those reported in the literature from lab assays. The meat by-products also showed their suitability. Once we moved on to animal skin subproducts, the collagen extraction was demonstrated.

Carotenoid (astaxanthin) production was optimized at semi-industrial scale. An alkaline pretreatment step to improve sugar release was optimized; in addition, different enzymatic hydrolysis trials have been performed in order to choose the best enzymatic cocktail and parameters (pH, temperature, dosage, time of reaction) at pilot scale. Combination of alkaline pretreatment (0,3 M, 10% (w/v) SCG loading at 60°C for 6 hours) and enzymatic hydrolysis using Celluclast 1.5 L and Xylanase 2X at 0,5% loading at milder conditions (55°C, pH 5) gave a yield of 5.14 g of glucose per liter. *Xanthophyllomyces dendrorhous* (formerly *Phaffia rhodozyma*) was selected for the astaxanthin production due that *Xanthophyllomyces dendrorhous* is considered by European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) to be suitable for the qualified presumption of safety (QPS) pre-assessment that covers safety concerns for humans, animals and the environment. Maximum yield of astaxanthin production achieved was 0.7 grams per kg of SCG. This yield is smaller than the yield reported with *Sporobolomyces roseus*, a fact that suggests that *S. roseus* seems to be a better candidate for the production of carotenoids from SCG. But as commented above, the choice of the *X. dendrorhous* was due that this yeast is considered as qualified presumption of safety by EFSA.

Producing organic fertilizer from blood subproducts was also demonstrated at semi-industrial scale showing its viability and feasibility. The process involves a chemical hydrolysis of the animal blood.

Extraction of coffee oil was achieved with batches of 3Kg of dried SCGs. The solvent used for the extraction was n-hexane. The yield obtained was 14% w/w, from all the feedstock and solvent used, the 14% was coffee oil. Nevertheless, considering that the SCG contained a 14.62% of total fat, the 95% of the available coffee oil was extracted.

For the polyphenols extraction, the yield was 17.62 mg gallic acid equivalents per gram of SCG. The bioprocesses were optimized achieving an efficiency of the process of 95%, which demonstrates the feasibility of the process selected.

The economic analysis of the blood product production process shows that it can be profitable and scalable. The profitability of the process depends on the sales price of the product and the price of the feedstock. In the scenario where the sales price is low, there is a loss in the first year, but the process becomes profitable in the second year and remains profitable for the rest of the 10 years. The sales price has a greater impact on the profitability of the process than the scenario type.

The economic analysis of the SCG coffee oil extraction with hexane shows that the process is not profitable. Despite that almost 100% of the total available fat is extracted, the process is not economically profitable due that the Soxhlet design could not fit more SCG in the Pilot trial and due that there is a 7% loss of hexane solvent in the process. As shown in Pilot 2, the coffee oil extraction is more favorable with Supercritical CO₂.

It is important to note that the economic analysis is based on a number of assumptions, such as the cost of energy, the cost of feedstock, and the sales price of the product. These assumptions may change in the future, which could impact the profitability of the process.

Overall, the economic analysis suggests that the production of SCG oil is a viable business opportunity. However, it is important to carefully consider all of the factors involved before making an investment decision.

The economic analysis of the carotenoid extraction process shows that, with the current data, the process is not feasible. This is because the amount of carotenoid produced are too low to reach gains in the market. However, the analysis also shows that the process is scalable. This means that with a higher carotenoid production yield, the process could become feasible.

Overall, the analysis suggests that the carotenoid extraction process has the potential to be a viable business opportunity. However, more research and development is needed to optimize the process as for example finding yeasts with higher carotenoid production yield to increase the production.

The economic analysis for production and commercialization of gelatine shows that the process can be profitable from the second year with profit margins around 70-80%. The economic analysis shows that the process is feasible and scalable showing exponential growth and stabilization.

Similar to the gelatine production, the economic analysis for production and commercialization of hydrolyzed collagen shows that the process can be profitable from the second year with profit margins around 60-80%.

The scalability and profitability of the process of polyphenols extraction shows that in the first scenario where the sale price is low, the first year there is a 59% maximum gain and 30% minimum, and it continues increasing until a maximum gain of 79%. In this case the sales price affects way more than the scenario type.

Therefore, the gelatine, hydrolyzed collagen, hydrolyzed blood production and polyphenols extraction are the processes more favorables in terms of economic profitability while coffee oil extraction with hexane and carotenoids production showed loss of gains.

6. References

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